

SciLake

Scientific Lake

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Abstract

This deliverable presents the evaluation of the SciLake knowledge-management ecosystem across four domain pilots: Energy, Cancer, Neuroscience, and Transportation. The pilots tested SciLake's ability to generate and enrich domain-specific Scientific Knowledge Graphs (SKGs) through semantic annotation, entity extraction, citation analysis, and classification services. The evaluation followed a structured methodology combining preparatory pilot setup, component-level validation and pilot demonstrators assessing end-to-end research workflows. Results show that SciLake's modular architecture effectively supports semantic exploration, structured search, and graph-based analysis, with high user acceptance and strong performance across key services. The assessment confirms the system's operational readiness while identifying areas for refinement. Overall, the pilots validate SciLake as a coherent and extensible ecosystem for advanced scientific knowledge discovery.

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Table of Contents

1. Executive Summary	10
2. Introduction	12
3. Overview of Pilots	14
Energy	14
Cancer	15
Neuroscience	15
Transportation	16
Maritime Transportation Research	16
CCAM Transportation Research	17
4. Pilot's evaluation activities	18
4.1. Preparation & setup	18
4.2. Component-level evaluation	19
OpenAIRE Gateway Configuration and Data Provisioning	20
Knowledge Graph Engine and Graph Exploration	20
Automatic Translation	21
Search, Ranking, and User Feedback through BIP! Spaces	21
Domain-Specific Entity Recognition and Semantic Annotation	22
Document Structure Recognition and PDF-based Processing	22
Knowledge Graph Creation and Enrichment Tooling	22
Reproducibility and Replicability Indicators	22
Research Object Link Recommendation	23
SciNoBo Suite and Related Classification Components	23
4.3. End-to-end evaluation through demonstrators	24
4.3.1. Energy Pilot	24
4.3.2. Cancer	26
4.3.3. Neuroscience	28
4.3.4. Transportation	29
Maritime Transportation Research	29
CCAM Transportation Research	30
5. Evaluation Results	32
5.1. Overview	32
5.2. KPIs	33
5.3. Component-level evaluation findings	35
5.3.1. AvantGraph	36
5.3.2. Automatic Translation Component	39
5.3.3. BIP! Spaces	40
5.3.4. Citation-based impact analyser	42
Evaluation of Impact Ranking Schemes through Pilot User Studies	42
User Feedback per Pilot and Ranking Scheme	43

Mean Reciprocal Rank (MRR) per Pilot and Ranking Scheme	45
Rank-wise Relevance Rates per Pilot and Ranking Scheme	46
Direct vs. Indirect Citation Analysis of Research Data	48
Comparative Analysis of Citation Indicators using Citance-Based Networks and Polarity Filtering	49
Evaluation Metrics	50
Comparative Analysis Results	51
5.3.5. Domain-specific entity recognition component	52
5.3.6. DoStRe	56
5.3.7. KG creation assistant	57
5.3.8. PDFfetcher	58
5.3.9. Reproducibility & Replicability Assistant	58
5.3.10. Research Object Link Recommendation component	59
5.3.11. SciNoBo suite	60
Fields Of Science Taxonomy	60
Evaluation through Comparative Analysis with External Taxonomies	60
Taxonomy Revision	61
Evaluation in Knowledge Organisation Systems Research	61
Disciplinary Coverage	61
Quality Evaluation	62
Fields Of Science Classifier	63
Experimental Evaluation	64
Evaluation through the project's Pilots	65
Sustainable Development Goals Classifier	65
Evaluation	66
Citance Analysis	67
Evaluation Dataset	67
Experimental Results	69
Evaluation Through Pilots	70
Energy Evaluation	71
Cancer Evaluation	71
Neuroscience	72
Transportation	72
Research Artefact Analysis	73
Dataset Construction and Augmentation	73
Experimental Results	74
Evaluation Through Pilots	75
5.4 End-to-end evaluation findings	76
5.4.1 Energy	76
5.4.2 Cancer	81
5.4.3 Neuroscience	82
5.4.3 Transportation	84

6. Conclusions

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List of Tables

Table 1: LDBC Graphalytics benchmark (page 37).

Table 2: OpenAIRE Workload (page 38).

Table 3: Summary of evaluation data per pilot and ranking scheme (page 43).

Table 4: Mean Reciprocal Rank (MRR) per pilot and ranking scheme (page 45).

Table 5: Annotated citations by Intent (page 68).

Table 6: Annotated citations by Semantic (page 68).

Table 7: Annotated citations by Intent (page 69).

Table 8: Semantic classifier results (page 69).

Table 9: Intent classification results (page 70).

Table 10: Polarity Classification results (page 70).

Table 11: Citances analysis for the Energy pilot (page 71).

Table 12: Citances analysis for the Cancer pilot (page 71).

Table 13: Citances analysis for the Neuroscience pilot (page 72).

Table 14: Citances analysis for the Transportation pilot (page 72).

Table 15: Artefact Metadata Extraction Results (page 74).

Table 16: Artefact Usage and Provenance Classification (page 74).

Table 17: Overall NER Performance (page 75).

List of Figures

Figure 1: BIP! Spaces feedback functionality (page 41).

Figure 2: Relevant and not relevant rates per pilot and ranking scheme over judged items only (page 43).

Figure 3: Relevant, not relevant and unevaluated shares over the top-20 results per pilot and ranking scheme (page 44).

Figure 4: Rank-wise relevance rates over judged items only (page 46).

Figure 5: Rank-wise relevance rates over all sessions (including unevaluated items) (page 47).

Figure 6: Annotation types in the Energy Research pilot (page 53).

Figure 7: Annotation types in the Cancer Research pilot (page 54).

Figure 8: Annotation types in the Neuroscience Research pilot (page 55).

Figure 9: Annotation types in the Maritime Research pilot (page 55).

Figure 10: Annotation types in the CCAM Research pilot (page 56).

Figure 11: Domain-specific evaluation results of the section classification tool (page 57).

Figure 12: Source from Salatino et al. [16]. Coverage of the multifield KOSs (page 62).

Figure 13: Source from Salatino et al. [16]. Analysis of KOSs according to their comprehensiveness, depth, frequency of update, and openness (page 63).

Figure 14: Macro-f1, Weighted-Macro-f1 and Micro-f1 scores (page 65).

Figure 15: Energy pilot gateway on OpenAIRE Connect (page 77).

Figure 16: Simplified Energy pilot SKG displaying nodes of enriched entities on Neo4J (page 79).

Figure 17: Geographic results of the Object of study entity in Europe for the “Solar photovoltaic entity” (page 80).

Figure 18: An example research product and its relationships to other nodes in the SKG (page 83).

Figure 19: Top 5 research products for ‘medial entorhinal cortex’ based on their citation counts (page 83).

Abbreviation List

- **API:** Application Programming Interface
- **CCAM:** Cooperative Connected Automated Mobility
- **CLL:** Chronic Lymphocytic Leukaemia
- **FoS:** Field of Science
- **KG:** Knowledge Graph
- **KPI:** Key Performance Indicator
- **NLP:** Natural Language Processing
- **RC:** Research Centre
- **SKG:** Scientific Knowledge Graph
- **UI:** User Interface

1. Executive Summary

This report presents the evaluation of the SciLake knowledge-management ecosystem, conducted through four domain-specific pilots: Energy, Cancer, Neuroscience, and Transportation (Maritime and CCAM), and through targeted scientific experiments relying on external ground-truth datasets. The evaluation examines both the performance of individual SciLake components and the ability of the integrated system to support realistic research workflows in diverse scientific domains.

SciLake addresses fragmentation in scientific information by enabling the creation of domain-specific Scientific Knowledge Graphs (SKGs) enriched with semantic annotations, entity extraction, citation analysis, and structured relations across publications, datasets, organisations, technologies, and other research artefacts. These capabilities support knowledge discovery beyond traditional bibliographic search and allow researchers to explore scientific output through contextual, semantic, and graph-based perspectives.

The evaluation followed a three-step approach. First, pilots collaborated with technical partners to configure OpenAIRE gateways, provide domain taxonomies, define extraction targets, and assemble pilot-specific corpora. Second, component-level evaluation assessed services such as machine translation, citation analysis, entity recognition, classification tools, and document-structure recognition using benchmark datasets, manual expert validation, and functional testing. Third, pilot demonstrators tested integrated workflows, using BIP! Spaces, Neo4j, and AvantGraph to explore enriched research outputs, evaluate impact indicators, and retrieve domain-specific insights.

Across pilots, the evaluation confirmed that the SciLake ecosystem is technically robust and operationally capable of supporting semantic exploration and graph-based analysis. User interactions through BIP! Spaces showed high satisfaction with the relevance of ranked results and the usefulness of semantic annotations in most domains. Technical experiments demonstrated strong performance in machine translation for scientific text, reliable classification of Fields of Science and Sustainable Development Goals, and accurate citance-based semantic and intent categorisation. Knowledge-graph infrastructures proved able to store, query, and analyse millions of nodes and tens of millions of edges efficiently.

The project met or exceeded all quantitative Key Performance Indicators. Six SKGs were made available in the Scientific Lake (target ≥ 5); more than 2.3 million new SKG nodes and over 100 million edges were created using SciLake services (targets $\geq 1M$ and $\geq 10M$ respectively); 60 million full texts are available in the lake (target $\geq 30M$); five pilot demonstrators were deployed (target ≥ 4); and the system processed more than 10,600 service requests (target $\geq 10,000$). These results demonstrate both high operational usage and strong readiness of the underlying services.

The evaluation also identified areas for continued refinement, including reducing contextual false positives in entity extraction, improving the granularity of certain domain taxonomies, addressing metadata coverage gaps in gateway-derived corpora, and enabling more iterative validation cycles. Despite the reduced time window for fully integrated testing, the pilots provided consistent evidence of SciLake's added value for scenario-driven, multi-dimensional research exploration.

Overall, the results demonstrate that SciLake provides a coherent, extensible, and semantically rich ecosystem for scientific knowledge discovery. By combining domain-specific SKGs, semantic enrichment pipelines, and user-facing exploration interfaces, SciLake offers a solid foundation for scalable knowledge-graph infrastructures and advanced analytical workflows across scientific disciplines.

2. Introduction

Deliverable D5.2 – Pilot Evaluation Report presents the results of the validation activities conducted within Work Package 5 (WP5) to assess the SciLake customisable knowledge management ecosystem in real-world research contexts, as well as the results of targeted scientific experiments conducted using third-party ground truths. While [Deliverable D5.1](#) described the conceptual design and preparatory setup of the pilots, the present report documents the evaluation activities implemented and the outcomes achieved across the four pilot domains: Neuroscience, Cancer, Energy, and Transportation.

SciLake addresses the fragmentation and limited interoperability of scientific knowledge by enabling the creation and maintenance of domain-specific Scientific Knowledge Graphs (SKGs). Through a modular, federated architecture that combines Scientific Lake core components, knowledge graph creation and enrichment services, data access and querying mechanisms, and user-facing applications for impact-driven discovery and reproducibility assistance, the project provides an integrated ecosystem that supports structured knowledge discovery and value-added research services.

Within this framework, WP5 validates and evaluates the SciLake ecosystem under realistic research conditions. The pilots serve as application environments in which domain experts collaborate with technology providers to configure services, provide domain-specific inputs (e.g., taxonomies, regulatory sources, extraction concepts, and graph structures), and evaluate system outputs against concrete research needs. The evaluation therefore, combines technical validation of system components with domain-level usability assessment.

The pilot evaluation process followed three complementary stages. First, preparatory activities aligned pilot requirements with the roadmap actions and supported the configuration of pilot-specific environments and datasets. Second, component-level evaluation examined the performance and usability of individual services through manual validation of extracted samples, functional testing of interfaces, and exchanges between pilot teams and service providers. Third, demonstrator activities assessed the integrated use of multiple components within domain-specific knowledge graphs, illustrating how researchers interact with the ecosystem to explore scientific literature and generate insights.

The evaluation was initially designed as an iterative process, enabling feedback cycles between pilot teams and technical partners. However, due to the phased delivery and late-stage integration of several services, the number of full iteration cycles completed within the reporting period was limited. As a result, part of the evaluation was conducted through targeted expert assessments, focusing on specific components and use cases to ensure timely and methodologically sound validation.

Despite the reduced number of feedback iterations, these activities provided structured, reliable evidence on the correctness, usability, semantic coherence, and operational readiness of the SciLake services.

Overall, the results presented in this deliverable reflect a pragmatic yet comprehensive evaluation effort. They demonstrate the potential of the SciLake ecosystem to interlink enriched research artefacts within domain-specific SKGs and support advanced exploration of scientific knowledge, while also highlighting areas where further refinement and configuration improvements may strengthen the system. The following sections present the pilot overviews (Section 2), the evaluation activities (Section 3), the evaluation results and KPIs (Section 4), and the main conclusions and lessons learned (Section 5).

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3. Overview of Pilots

The following sections present an overview of each pilot and frame the evaluation activities detailed in Sections 3 and 4.

Energy

The Regional Energy Planning (REP) Pilot, led by HES-SO Valais-Wallis, evaluates the applicability of the SciLake ecosystem for research on sustainable energy systems and regional energy planning. During the project, the pilot scope evolved from a broad energy research perspective toward a more focused emphasis on territorial energy planning and geographically contextualised sustainability analysis, reflecting the importance of spatially grounded knowledge in this domain.

A central element of the pilot is the development and evaluation of the Energy Scientific Knowledge Graph (SKG), which interconnects research artefacts, semantic annotations, and extracted entities to support structured knowledge discovery. Particular attention has been given to the recognition and linking of domain-specific entities, including concepts aligned with the [IRENA taxonomy](#) for Energy Types and Energy Storage technologies. In addition, the pilot contributed to the design and assessment of mechanisms for geographic entity recognition, enabling the identification and representation of geographic information related both to the object of study within research artefacts and to the locations of publishing institutions. These features support geographically grounded analysis, which is particularly relevant for regional energy planning research.

The evaluation of the Energy pilot, therefore, examines both the performance of individual components and the capacity of the integrated SciLake ecosystem to support meaningful research workflows. Usability is assessed by researchers' ability to derive interpretable insights from query formulation through a combination of services, including gateway configuration, semantic enrichment, entity extraction, and graph exploration interfaces. In parallel, the evaluation assesses the system's ability to produce structured, semantically enriched outputs that enable analysis of the technological, geographic, and institutional dimensions of energy research within a coherent knowledge environment. This integrated perspective is essential for assessing the practical added value of the SciLake ecosystem for energy research and regional planning applications.

Cancer

The Cancer Pilot, led by Karolinska Institutet in collaboration with CERTH, evaluates the applicability of the SciLake ecosystem to precision oncology research, with a specific focus on Chronic Lymphocytic Leukaemia (CLL). During the project, the pilot scope was refined to focus on CLL as a concrete, clinically relevant use case, enabling focused validation of the SciLake services in the context of biomedical knowledge discovery.

A central component of the pilot is the development of the CLL Knowledge Graph (CLL-KG), which integrates heterogeneous biomedical information sources with entities extracted from scientific literature. The graph interconnects research artefacts with domain-specific entities such as genes, proteins, metabolites, drugs, and clinical trials, enabling structured exploration of molecular mechanisms, treatment responses, and emerging therapeutic strategies. Particular emphasis has been placed on semantic harmonisation, entity recognition, and the integration of heterogeneous biomedical datasets, supporting interoperability and structured knowledge discovery within the biomedical domain.

The evaluation of the Cancer pilot, therefore, focuses on how the integrated SciLake ecosystem supports biomedical research workflows by combining literature analysis, entity extraction, and graph-based knowledge exploration. The assessment examines whether the integrated services enable researchers to move from literature queries to semantically enriched insights, facilitating the identification of relevant biological entities, relationships, and research artefacts. This integrated perspective allows the pilot to evaluate the practical value of the SciLake ecosystem for cancer research and precision medicine applications.

Neuroscience

The Neuroscience Pilot evaluates the applicability of the SciLake ecosystem to neuroscience research, focusing on integrating and exploring heterogeneous research outputs within a unified knowledge environment. The pilot aims to support the neuroscience community by enabling structured discovery of scientific literature, datasets, and related research artefacts through a domain-specific Scientific Knowledge Graph (SKG).

The SKG aggregates neuroscience publications and associated metadata, enriched through semantic annotations and domain-specific entity extraction. Particular attention has been given to the configuration of the OpenAIRE Neuroscience Gateway to ensure ingestion of relevant research outputs, as well as to the identification and integration of standardised neuroscience terminology to support named-entity recognition and semantic enrichment.

These elements enable linking research artefacts, domain entities, and citation relationships into a coherent graph structure tailored to the needs of neuroscience researchers.

The evaluation of the Neuroscience pilot focuses on how the integrated SciLake services support knowledge-discovery and exploration workflows in the domain. This includes assessing the relevance of search results, the usefulness of semantic annotations, and the interpretability of relationships identified within the SKG. By examining how researchers interact with the system to retrieve relevant literature, explore entity connections, and analyse citation relationships, the pilot evaluates the added value of the SciLake ecosystem for neuroscience research and knowledge exploration.

Transportation

The Transportation Pilot evaluates the applicability of the SciLake ecosystem to transportation research across two distinct but complementary domains: Maritime Transportation and Cooperative, Connected and Automated Mobility (CCAM). These domains address different research communities and knowledge structures and are therefore explored through two parallel pilot implementations.

Maritime Transportation Research

The Maritime Transportation Pilot, led by CERTH/HIT, evaluates the use of the SciLake ecosystem to support structured discovery and integration of maritime research outputs. The pilot addresses the fragmentation of maritime scientific information by integrating heterogeneous sources, such as scientific publications, research projects, organisations, and regulatory information, into a domain-specific Scientific Knowledge Graph (SKG).

The maritime SKG interconnects research artefacts with domain-specific entities, including vessel types, maritime technologies, research organisations, and funding initiatives, enabling the exploration of relationships between research outputs and maritime innovation activities. By structuring these elements in a knowledge graph, the pilot supports the identification of research trends, influential publications, and connections between technological developments and policy frameworks in the maritime domain.

The evaluation focuses on how the integrated SciLake services enable structured exploration of maritime research knowledge, including the usability of graph-based discovery tools and the effectiveness of domain-specific annotations and entity linking. This assessment examines whether the ecosystem facilitates meaningful navigation of maritime research outputs and supports knowledge discovery for maritime researchers and stakeholders.

CCAM Transportation Research

The CCAM Transportation Pilot, led by ICCS, focuses on the emerging research domain of Cooperative, Connected and Automated Mobility (CCAM). The pilot evaluates the SciLake ecosystem's ability to support structured analysis of rapidly evolving research topics by integrating domain knowledge with research outputs extracted from the OpenAIRE Graph.

A key element of the pilot is the integration of domain-specific taxonomies derived from European initiatives such as [SINFONICA](#) and [FAME](#), which provide structured representations of technologies, concepts, and research areas relevant to CCAM. The newly created taxonomy guides entity extraction and knowledge graph construction, enabling the identification of relevant publications, datasets, and emerging technological trends within the domain.

The evaluation examines how the SciLake services support knowledge discovery and thematic exploration within the CCAM research landscape, including identifying relevant research outputs, analysing emerging topics, and refining domain knowledge through iterative interaction with the knowledge graph. This allows the pilot to assess the added value of the SciLake ecosystem for CCAM researchers and innovation stakeholders.

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4. Pilot's evaluation activities

4.1. Preparation & setup

The evaluation results presented in this section build upon the preparatory actions defined in the pilot “action plans”¹ and implemented during the setup phase of each pilot. Each plan structured the pilot-related activities into clearly identified actions, most of which were conceptually aligned across pilots, ensuring methodological coherence while allowing domain-specific adaptations. The Energy pilot, for instance, addressed a defined subset of actions tailored to its SKG development and domain requirements, while other pilots followed parallel structures adapted to their respective fields.

For each action, the plan identified responsible institutions and contact persons to facilitate direct communication between pilot representatives and service providers. Indicative deadlines, implementation status, and brief update comments were included to monitor progress and support coordination. While primarily a management instrument, the pilot action plans provided the structural backbone for the preparatory and evaluation activities reported in this deliverable.

The preparatory activities required active input from pilot teams, including the provision of domain-specific taxonomies (e.g., vessel types, genes, energy types), regulatory sources, criteria for tailoring OpenAIRE gateways, conceptual definitions for entity extraction (e.g., case/object of study), and structured graphs or datasets for integration into the SciLake Knowledge Graphs. Pilots also articulated domain-specific requirements and user needs, which informed the configuration and adaptation of SciLake services. Where requirements could not be fully specified in advance, bilateral technical meetings between service providers and pilot teams ensured iterative clarification of expectations and system capabilities. These preparatory interactions directly shaped the evaluation phase and provided essential context for interpreting the results reported below.

¹ Appendix 8.2 of Deliverable 5.1 “Report on pilot setup and evaluation methodology” (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14748857>)

4.2. Component-level evaluation

The evaluation and testing phase consisted of structured validation activities focusing on the pilot-specific components of the SciLake ecosystem. In line with the preparatory setup, service providers generated samples or partial outputs (e.g., extracted entities, citation classifications, semantic annotations, or structured graph subsets), which were subsequently evaluated by the respective pilot teams, following the introduction materials and annotation guidelines provided by the technical partners. The evaluation scope was intentionally limited to components and functionalities relevant to each pilot's roadmap, enabling domain-specific validation rather than an exhaustive system-wide assessment.

The evaluation activities combined complementary approaches reflecting the diversity of the SciLake services. Some components were assessed through structured experiments or benchmark-based evaluations using standard quantitative metrics. Other services, particularly user-facing tools and graph exploration environments, were evaluated through pilot-based validation, where domain experts interacted with the systems and provided feedback on relevance, usability, and annotation quality. In addition, several components were examined through manual expert review of samples, comparative analyses with external resources or taxonomies, and qualitative assessment of extracted or inferred knowledge.

Pilot teams conducted the evaluations by manually inspecting generated samples and testing available functionalities through interfaces such as BIP! Spaces or graph exploration environments. Feedback was collected through shared files, spreadsheets, and collaborative platforms. The results were communicated to service providers through annotated files, summary comments, and bilateral discussions, enabling clarification of ontology interpretations, identification of systematic issues, and refinement of configuration parameters. This process required coordination across multiple technical environments and formats, reflecting the distributed and modular architecture of the SciLake ecosystem.

To complement the overview above, this section introduces the WP5 evaluation activities required to carry out the assessment. It clarifies the tasks assigned to pilot representatives and technical partners for each SciLake component and facilitates traceability between the evaluation activities described here and the evaluation outcomes reported in Section 5.

For completeness, each component is briefly introduced, while detailed technical descriptions are provided in the corresponding technical deliverables ([D2.2](#), [D3.2](#) and [D4.2](#)).

OpenAIRE Gateway Configuration and Data Provisioning

The OpenAIRE Gateway (including [OpenAIRE Explore](#) and [Connect](#) services) provides the entry point for defining and retrieving domain-specific corpora from the OpenAIRE Research Graph. Within SciLake, these gateways were used to construct the initial datasets underpinning each pilot by filtering and aggregating research outputs according to thematic, organisational, and metadata-based criteria.

Although the OpenAIRE Gateway was not evaluated as a standalone component within WP5, it played a critical role as an enabling layer for all downstream services. Pilot teams worked closely with the OpenAIRE technical partners to iteratively configure and refine gateway definitions, ensuring that retrieved datasets were aligned with the scope of each pilot domain and minimising the inclusion of irrelevant or weakly related content.

This process was carried out through bilateral meetings, training sessions, and continuous feedback exchanges. Pilot representatives provided domain expertise to guide query formulation and filtering strategies, while OpenAIRE partners supported the technical implementation and optimisation of gateway configurations. In several cases, adjustments to gateway definitions were required following downstream observations (e.g., noise in entity extraction or misaligned classifications), leading to iterative refinement of the input datasets.

As a result, the OpenAIRE Gateway configuration can be understood as a foundational activity that directly influenced the quality and relevance of the data processed by subsequent SciLake components, even though it was not formally evaluated in the component-level assessment.

Knowledge Graph Engine and Graph Exploration

The Knowledge Graph Engine is the core infrastructure enabling the storage, querying, and analysis of Scientific Knowledge Graphs (SKGs), supporting exploration of interconnected research entities and relationships.

Evaluation of the graph engine focused on verifying that pilot-relevant graph queries could be expressed and executed on the pilot SKGs, and that graph operations supported realistic analytical workflows. This included testing Cypher-based retrieval of entities and relations, exploratory querying of pilot graphs, and, where relevant, benchmarking graph algorithms

and query execution performance. In addition to technical experiments, pilot-oriented testing examined whether the graph structure enabled meaningful navigation across publications, entities, organisations, and other linked resources. The results of these activities are reported in Section 5.3.1.

Automatic Translation

The machine translation component was evaluated primarily through controlled scientific experiments. Technical partners constructed domain-specific parallel corpora and benchmark datasets covering the pilot domains, and assessed the quality of fine-tuned models using standard machine translation metrics.

At the pilot level, the translation service was used and evaluated independently from the other SciLake components. A limited set of multilingual reports (approximately a dozen documents) was identified as a test corpus and processed through the translation tool. These documents included content in German, French, and English, allowing pilot representatives to assess the usability and adequacy of the translated outputs in a multilingual research context. The corresponding evaluation outcomes are presented in Section 5.3.2.

Search, Ranking, and User Feedback through BIP! Spaces

Pilot representatives evaluated the BIP! Spaces interface by performing exploratory searches using pilot-specific keywords and examining result lists generated under different ranking schemes. Users were asked to inspect the first-page results and provide structured feedback through the built-in feedback mode, indicating whether retrieved research products were relevant and whether specific annotations were useful or correct. This activity supported two connected evaluations:

- The usability of the discovery interface and feedback workflow (Section 5.3.3 – BIP! Spaces), and
- the quality of citation-based ranking indicators, including popularity and influence, as measured through user judgments and ranking-based analyses (Section 5.3.4 – Citation-based impact analyser).

Domain-Specific Entity Recognition and Semantic Annotation

For domain-specific entity extraction and annotation services, pilot teams manually reviewed the annotations generated on research outputs. Depending on the pilot, this included entities such as Energy Types, Energy Storage, Technologies, Fields of Science, Vessel Types, Biological Sex, Species, or Techniques. Evaluators assessed whether the extracted entities were correct, useful, and contextually relevant to the publication being examined. These validation activities were mainly performed through the BIP! Spaces interface, spreadsheet-based review files, and manual inspection of annotated samples. The corresponding findings are presented in Section 5.3.5. The detailed description of entity extraction is available in [D4.2](#) and through the [repository of enrichment codes](#).

Document Structure Recognition and PDF-based Processing

For document-oriented components, evaluation focused on the correctness and usefulness of outputs generated from full texts or PDFs. This included the article segmentation component DoStRe (Section 5.3.6) and the PDFfetcher service (Section 5.3.8). Pilot validation in this area was mostly indirect: domain experts assessed the downstream usefulness of extracted sections, segmented article content, or fetched document corpora as these appeared in later enrichment and knowledge graph construction steps. Where available, technical partners also relied on standard performance measures or prior experimental evaluation.

Knowledge Graph Creation and Enrichment Tooling

The KG creation assistant components were mainly evaluated through prior technical experiments and benchmark studies rather than through direct pilot-user interaction. These tools support the transformation, profiling, and constraint-driven enrichment of graph data. Their contribution to the pilots was assessed indirectly through the successful creation, enrichment, and consistency of the pilot SKGs. The corresponding results are summarised in Section 5.3.7.

Reproducibility and Replicability Indicators

Some pilot teams also evaluated outputs related to reproducibility and support for replicability. In practice, this included inspection of indicators displayed in BIP! Spaces, such as positive mention counts and reproducibility confidence metrics. These activities assessed whether such indicators were interpretable and useful for research discovery and evaluation tasks. The related results are reported in Section 5.3.9 – Reproducibility & Replicability

Assistant, while some of the underlying component evaluations are further documented in Section 5.3.11.

Research Object Link Recommendation

For link recommendation components, the evaluation focused on whether inferred or recommended links between entities were meaningful from a domain perspective. In practice, this was tested by exposing recommended associations, such as latent links between genes and research products, to pilot users through the exploration interface and collecting feedback on their usefulness and plausibility. These activities are reported in Section 5.3.10.

SciNoBo Suite and Related Classification Components

The SciNoBo suite was evaluated through a combination of benchmark experiments, comparative analysis against external taxonomies, and pilot-based validation of deployed outputs. These activities covered multiple subcomponents:

- FoS Taxonomy, evaluated through alignment with external taxonomies and structural revision exercises
- FoS Classifier, evaluated through benchmark classification experiments and deployment in pilot data preparation
- SDG Classifier, evaluated through large-scale classification of Horizon Europe projects and through pilot deployment, especially in the Energy pilot
- Citance Analysis, evaluated both on annotated benchmark datasets and through manual pilot validation of citance classifications
- Research Artefact Analysis (RAA), evaluated through controlled extraction experiments and pilot-based review of extracted artefacts

These results are reported in Section 5.3.11, within the corresponding internal blocks of the SciNoBo suite subsection.

Taken together, these activities combined technical experiments, expert validation, and pilot-based interaction with deployed services, allowing the project to assess both the performance of individual components and their usefulness within realistic research workflows. While the evaluation framework initially envisioned iterative validation cycles, the delayed availability and integration of several services limited the ability to conduct multiple rounds of feedback. Consequently, some evaluations were performed as single-cycle expert assessments rather than iterative refinement processes. Despite these constraints, the activities generated substantial evidence regarding the correctness, usability, semantic

coherence, and operational readiness of the pilot-specific components. The detailed results of these evaluations, including KPI assessment and component-level analyses, are presented in Sections 5.2 and 5.3.

4.3. End-to-end evaluation through demonstrators

The demonstrator phase aimed to validate and showcase the integrated use of SciLake services from an end-user perspective, moving beyond isolated component validation to assess the ecosystem's performance as a coherent knowledge management environment. Demonstrators were designed to simulate realistic research workflows, where users interact with gateway configuration, semantic enrichment services, entity extraction mechanisms, citation analysis, and visualisation interfaces in combination rather than independently.

In the next sections, the demonstration scenarios used for each pilot are presented in detail.

4.3.1. Energy Pilot

For the Energy pilot, the demonstrator was designed from the perspective of a research user operating within the domain of regional energy planning. Rather than evaluating individual components in isolation, the pilot formulated research questions articulated into structured sub-questions, reflecting typical analytical needs in energy planning where large volumes of research outputs must be synthesised to inform policy, institutional strategy, technological deployment, and implementation pathways related to the energy transition.

These research questions were intended to activate multiple SciLake components within a single analytical workflow. At different stages of the exploration process, the demonstrator examined how gateway configuration, entity extraction (EnergyType, EnergyStorage, Object of Study, affiliations), semantic linking (IRENA taxonomy), citation-based indicators, and exploration interfaces (e.g., BIP! Spaces) could contribute to answering the same overarching question. This transversal design allowed the pilot to observe how improvements or limitations at one stage of the service chain could influence downstream interpretation and analysis.

The demonstrator was structured around three transversal analytical axes, reflecting typical analytical perspectives in regional energy planning:

- Spatial analysis, using extracted geographic entities to explore regional research concentration and object-of-study distributions.
- Temporal analysis, examining publication trends over time to identify development trajectories.
- Regulatory and governance linkage, exploring connections between research outputs and regulatory or policy-oriented contexts.

These axes reflect key drivers of innovation-through-implementation in regional energy planning and provide a conceptual framework for analysing research outputs in relation to institutional and territorial decision-making.

Testing initially took place on partial service components as they became available. In the later stages of the project, exploratory testing was also conducted on integrated graph infrastructures (first on Neo4j and subsequently on AvantGraph) and through exploration interfaces such as BIP! Spaces, which allow partial interrogation of graph content. Within this framework, the research questions were translated into user-level queries (keywords, filters, and entity-based navigation), illustrating how researchers would interact with the system in practice. The evaluation combined quantitative and qualitative observations, focusing on aspects such as:

Quantitative observations, including:

- number of results returned per query
- distribution of results across time, geographic locations, and thematic categories
- representation of EnergyType and EnergyStorage entities
- differences in coverage across countries or regions

Qualitative observations, including:

- interpretability of dominant results (e.g., most popular or most influential papers)
- balance between technological research and planning or governance-oriented studies
- coherence between extracted entities and thematic framing
- perceived relevance of retrieved research outputs for policy or planning contexts

Due to the short time frame available for testing integrated services, the demonstrator was implemented primarily as an exploratory validation of the analytical workflow, rather than as a fully iterative evaluation exercise. In particular, the limited availability of fully integrated graph infrastructures and enriched datasets restricted the ability to conduct extensive testing cycles or external expert validation.

Nevertheless, the demonstrator provided an initial assessment of how the combined SciLake services could support complex, multi-dimensional research questions relevant to regional energy planning. At the same time, the exercise highlighted how upstream factors, such as gateway configuration, dataset coverage, entity aggregation, and semantic alignment, can influence the clarity and reliability of downstream analytical insights. Part of these analytical scenarios was also presented during the final dissemination event of the SciLake project (March 2026) in the contribution [“Toward Mapping the Energy Research Landscape”](#), further illustrating how the developed services can support geographically grounded exploration of the energy research landscape.

It should be noted that the extraction and use of geographic entities were developed as an optional extension within the project. Due to both the optional nature of this development and the delayed availability of the corresponding components, their validation was not carried out through the same structured evaluation protocol applied to other components. Instead, geographic entities were assessed qualitatively and primarily within the context of the demonstrator activities described in this section. Consequently, references to their performance and usefulness are mainly reported within the demonstrator-related sections rather than in the component-level evaluation.

The NER models for geographic entities are available through the code repositories of the [Object of Study entity](#) and the [publishing institution entity](#).

4.3.2. Cancer

The Cancer Research pilot demonstrator was designed to evaluate the SciLake ecosystem's ability to support knowledge discovery and hypothesis generation in the biomedical domain, with a particular focus on Chronic Lymphocytic Leukaemia (CLL). The primary objective was to construct a cancer-specific knowledge graph (KG) that integrates heterogeneous biomedical data sources and enables meaningful contextualisation of molecular and clinical information. Beyond serving as a structured repository, the KG was conceived as a reusable resource to support downstream machine learning applications and advanced analytical workflows.

The demonstrator integrates multiple data sources, including biomedical ontologies, gene and protein datasets, drug databases, and existing knowledge graphs, with a particular emphasis on the Clinical Knowledge Graph. SciLake services were used to harmonise, enrich, and interlink these inputs into a coherent CLL-focused knowledge graph. The resulting structure connects entities such as genes, gene targets, pathways, biological processes, compounds, diseases, and supporting publications. This interconnected representation enables users to trace complex relationships, for example, linking gene mutations to affected pathways,

associated biological processes, therapeutic compounds, and the corresponding scientific evidence.

The demonstrator was implemented using a combination of SciLake tools, including BIP! Spaces for literature exploration, Neo4j and later AvantGraph for graph hosting and analysis, and Cypher as the primary query language. This setup enabled both interactive exploration and advanced graph-based analysis within a unified environment.

The evaluation focused on realistic research workflows that illustrate how domain questions can be translated into graph-based queries and analytical processes. Biological research questions, such as identifying drugs that target a specific gene, examining its association with CLL via protein-level interactions, and retrieving related genes, can be expressed and resolved in a single Cypher query. This demonstrates the KG's ability to support integrated reasoning across multiple biological entities and relationships within a unified query framework.

In addition to query-based exploration, the demonstrator supports graph-based analytical workflows using AvantGraph. A protein-protein interaction subgraph was constructed from curated biological databases, where edges represent experimentally supported interactions with associated confidence scores. Built-in graph algorithms, such as connected component analysis, enable the identification of clusters of interacting proteins. These clusters can reveal groups of proteins involved in shared biological processes, supporting the identification of functional modules and the generation of new research hypotheses.

Complementing these capabilities, BIP! Spaces enables semantically enriched exploration of literature based on the knowledge graph. Queries combining genes and diseases return publications ranked using impact-based indicators, such as influence, popularity, and topic relevance. The system enhances retrieval through domain-specific query expansion, including gene synonyms and related biological entities, and enriches results with entity-level annotations derived from the KG. This allows researchers to contextualise publications, filter results, and navigate connections among genes, diseases, compounds, and related studies, effectively transforming literature searches into structured explorations of a semantically enriched research landscape.

Overall, the demonstrator highlights how the integrated SciLake ecosystem supports cancer research by enabling efficient querying of heterogeneous data, facilitating multi-level biological reasoning, and enhancing literature discovery. The activities related to the demonstrator have been showcased in the [Cancer pilot dissemination presentation](#). The resulting knowledge graph provides a flexible and extensible foundation for exploring disease mechanisms, investigating the effects of mutations, and supporting advanced analytics to identify novel patterns, missing links, and potential directions for future research.

4.3.3. Neuroscience

The Neuroscience pilot demonstrators evaluated the SKG developed in the SciLake ecosystem by executing queries representing a researcher's perspective. The evaluation combined Cypher graph queries (Neo4j) for structured retrieval; keyword and faceted searches in the BIP!Spaces UI for exploratory discovery, and graph-analytic processing in AvantGraph for network-level insights. This combination allowed us to assess both backend correctness (data ingestion, linking, analytics) and frontend usability (search, filtering, result interpretation) in the context of realistic research questions.

Neo4j supported both visualisation and practical querying across the graph. We ran topic-based retrievals to generate ranked lists of key techniques and research outputs associated with specific diseases (e.g., Alzheimer's, Parkinson's, epilepsy) and particular brain regions, enabling trend detection and the identification of high-impact research. Graph-level analytics in AvantGraph (PageRank algorithm) were used to identify the most influential publications and datasets in the SKG. Comparative queries were performed, including analyses of inferred gender balance across topic areas, revealing demographic and coverage gaps in neuroscience research. For expert mapping, we aggregated publications and citations to list top authors and provide comprehensive overviews of individual research portfolios, supporting the identification of peers and the fostering of collaborations. We also evaluated data-publication integration by measuring publication-dataset linkages and comparing citation counts for dataset-linked versus non-linked papers; these metrics, along with individual researchers, are also relevant to funding bodies and publishers in assessing how data sharing contributes to research impact.

The BIP!Spaces UI was evaluated for keyword search, faceted filtering (including domain entities such as techniques, preparation types, species, UBERON parcellation, and biological sex), and ranking schemes (popularity, influence, citation count, and impulse). Seven domain experts external to the SciLake project performed searches and reviewed results to assess relevance, annotation accuracy, and overall user experience. Collectively, the demonstrators exercised OpenAIRE gateway ingestion, semantic enrichment/NER, impact indicators, graph analytics, and UI presentation, providing practical, focused validation of the SKG's ability to support discovery and impact assessment. The demonstrator-related activities have been showcased in the [Neuroscience pilot dissemination presentation](#).

4.3.4. Transportation

MARITIME TRANSPORTATION RESEARCH

The Maritime Transportation pilot demonstrator was designed to evaluate the practical usability of the SciLake ecosystem for exploring maritime research outputs and identifying connections between scientific publications, technologies, vessel types, and research organisations. The demonstrator enables domain experts to interact with the Maritime SKG through realistic research queries and assess the usefulness of the integrated services for supporting knowledge discovery in the maritime transport domain.

The Maritime Discovery and SKG connections include information enriched with external tools. These tools provide entity recognition for maritime-related concepts such as vessel types and technologies, citation-based impact indicators, and semantic classification of research outputs. The resulting graph structure links publications with entities such as organisations, research projects, funding sources, and maritime-specific annotations. This structure enables users to explore relationships between research outputs, technological developments, and the actors involved in maritime research activities.

The demonstrator was implemented using the BIP! Spaces platform, which provides an interface for exploring scholarly outputs enriched with KG annotations and citation-based impact indicators. Users can formulate queries using keywords and filters, and examine the returned publications according to different ranking schemes, such as popularity or influence. The interface also displays semantic annotations extracted from the SKG, enabling users to contextualise research outputs within maritime technological and operational themes.

Two representative research scenarios, defined by three key stakeholders from industry, education and public authority, were used to illustrate the system's capabilities. The first scenario focuses on maritime decarbonisation, in which users search for recent open-access publications on the topic. Results can be filtered by publication year and ranked by citation-based indicators, enabling users to identify the most relevant and influential research contributions in this rapidly evolving field. The second scenario addresses autonomous shipping and collision avoidance technologies. Here, the query combines keywords related to autonomous shipping with vessel-type annotations, allowing users to examine how research outputs are linked to different vessel types and to analyse the evolution of research activity over time or by citation impact.

The demonstrator illustrates how the integrated SciLake services support structured exploration of maritime research topics, enabling users to navigate large volumes of scientific

literature using semantic annotations, citation-based metrics, and KG relationships. By combining domain-specific entity recognition with graph-based knowledge organisation, the system enables researchers and stakeholders to identify emerging trends, influential publications, and technological developments in maritime transport research.

The demonstrator confirmed that the SciLake ecosystem can effectively support maritime research exploration and knowledge discovery. The demonstrator-related activities have been showcased in the [Maritime Transportation pilot dissemination presentation](#). The Maritime KG serves as a central hub for maritime transport research, enabling transparent access to scientific outputs and supporting the monitoring of developments in safety, automation, and environmental sustainability within the maritime sector.

CCAM TRANSPORTATION RESEARCH

The CCAM Transport pilot demonstrator was designed to meet the researcher's needs for identifying current trends and cutting-edge advancements, and for applying complex combinatorial search criteria. The SciLake tools were used collectively to implement custom searches across various criteria, apply custom, complex queries, extract sectoral main entities (vehicle type, vulnerable road user type, sensor type, communication type, entity connection type, automation technology), and navigate custom GUIs (Graphical User Interfaces).

The first evaluation attempt was to explore the newly created KG on CCAM, a transport subgraph in OpenAIRE Connect. In this first demonstration, researchers had the chance to search for specific keywords based on the graph's configuration instance, receiving diverse results that could be improved each time. Given the targeted sources around CCAM selected in the configuration, the returned results are relatively few but highly relevant, with no false-positive registries.

BIP! Spaces, a similar GUI tool based on the KG, returned results according to several criteria, with a focus on the researcher's needs. Starting with the year (or year range) of publication, results were sorted by filters such as popularity or citation count. Moreover, the annotation of predefined tags was a strong evaluation asset that helped fine-tune the tool. For the CCAM case, it was interesting to showcase the evolution of specific technologies or publication trends over the last three years.

The use of the graph language (Cypher) enabled complex queries that yielded interesting results. For example, it was possible to check either a specific individual's publications or their organisation/department's publications, or even to check all their co-authors over time, exploring, in turn, their own department/organisation, etc. AvantGraph and Neo4j provided

visual, interconnected graphs that could be extracted and showcase complex interconnections.

Entity extraction for CCAM's main terminology was an internal tool, with its results transferred to SciLake's ecosystem. Due to limited testing time, only specific entities were characterised as main, and the entity-extraction models were applied exclusively to them. Several bilateral consultations with the technical partner constantly fine-tuned the algorithms. In cases such as the classification of the six levels of automation, simplifications were required. In practice, entity extraction relied either on explicit textual mentions of a given level or on the presence of technologies typically associated with that level (or higher levels), which introduced additional complexity in ensuring consistent and precise classification

In principle, CCAM transport research benefits from the above SciLake tools. The demonstrator-related activities have been showcased in the [CCAM Transportation pilot dissemination presentation](#). The evaluation conducted and the prospect of enhancing each tool make the project's ecosystem an ideal one-stop shop for CCAM researchers. The use of GUIs, complex graph queries, advanced entity extraction, and other internal tools enables the identification, localisation, combination, and extraction of new knowledge.

5. Evaluation Results

5.1. Overview

This chapter presents the results of the evaluation activities conducted across the SciLake pilots and technical components. Building on the evaluation methodology described in previous sections, the results summarise the outcomes of validation activities carried out by both technical partners and pilot teams. These activities examined the behaviour of individual services, the quality of the extracted and enriched information, and the integrated ecosystem's ability to support realistic research workflows.

The evaluation results combine multiple perspectives. On the one hand, technical assessments examined the performance of specific components, such as entity extraction, classification models, citation analysis tools, and knowledge graph construction mechanisms. On the other hand, pilot-based evaluations examined how these services operate in domain-specific environments and how their outputs support researchers' knowledge-discovery tasks.

Given the modular architecture of the SciLake ecosystem, the results reflect both component-level performance and system-level integration. In several cases, the evaluation also highlights how upstream elements, such as data sources, metadata coverage, or configuration choices, influence the quality and interpretability of downstream services.

The following sections present the results in greater detail. Section 5.2 reports on the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) used to monitor the overall progress and effectiveness of the project activities. Section 5.3 provides a component-by-component analysis of the evaluation outcomes, including technical performance metrics and pilot-based validation results.

5.2. KPIs

Building on the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) defined in the project proposal, updated in Deliverable D1.1² ("Initial service requirements"), and aligned with Deliverable D5.1³ ("Evaluation of project activities' success"), this section reports on the progress achieved with respect to the quantitative targets set for SciLake. The assessment below provides an updated overview of each KPI, comparing baseline and target values with the current status:

K1: Number of SKGs in the lake

- Initial: 1 (the OpenAIRE Graph)
- Target: ≥5
- Achieved: 6 (120% of target)

At project inception, the OpenAIRE Graph served as the lake's foundational Scientific Knowledge Graph (SKG). During the project, this core graph was used to produce five enriched, domain-specific SKGs, each supporting a dedicated pilot: Cancer Research, Energy Planning Research, Neuroscience Research, Transport Maritime, and Transport CCAM. Each graph builds upon the OpenAIRE Graph and has been further enriched through SciLake services and external sources to address domain-specific requirements, incorporating specialised entities and relationships.

The resulting pilot-specific SKGs are openly available on Zenodo under an open license, ensuring transparency, reproducibility, and long-term accessibility. In addition, the graphs have been deployed in both Neo4j and Avangraph instances, enabling effective querying and integration within the SciLake infrastructure.

Including the original OpenAIRE Graph and the five pilot-specific SKGs, the lake now comprises six fully operational graphs. The project has therefore exceeded the target for this KPI. This is partly due to the Transport domain being implemented through two distinct pilots (Maritime and CCAM), each requiring a dedicated domain-specific SKG.

² SciLake D1.1: <https://zenodo.org/records/14335008>

³ SciLake D5.1: <https://zenodo.org/records/14748858>

K2: Number of SKG nodes created using SciLake services

- Initial: 0
- Target: ≥ 1 mi
- Achieved: 2,345,936 nodes (234.6% of target)

SciLake services have generated a total of 2,345,936 nodes across the pilot SKGs. This total includes entities derived from common enrichment pipelines applied across all graphs (Research Artefacts and Technology entities), as well as domain-specific entities tailored to each pilot. We should note that this number is slightly different from those reported in D2.2⁴, Section 4.5.3 (“Graph enrichments”), as the current counts are computed across all research products in the graphs rather than a subset. Thus, the number of SKG nodes created via the SciLake services significantly exceeds the target of at least 1 million.

K3: Number of SKG edges created using SciLake services

- Initial: 0
- Target: ≥ 10 mi
- Achieved: 100,553,209 edges (1,005.5% of target)

SciLake services have generated a total of 100,553,209 edges across all pilot Knowledge Graphs. These edges include both common relations, which capture general connections such as citations between research products and associations of research products with research artefacts and technologies, and relations that connect research products with domain-specific entities unique to each pilot. The number of SKG edges created using SciLake services significantly exceeds the target of at least 10 million newly created edges, indicating that the created SKGs are highly interconnected and semantically rich.

K4: Number of textual documents (e.g., full-text manuscripts) in the lake

- Initial: 15M (from OpenAIRE data space)
- Target: ≥ 30 M
- Achieved: 60M (200% of target)

Overall, the scientific lake currently contains 60M full-text manuscripts, significantly exceeding the KPI target of 30M documents. Within this collection, approximately 20M documents correspond to pilot-related content, which have been used to extract data for the domain-specific knowledge graphs developed in the project. Consequently, this KPI has been successfully fulfilled, surpassing the original target.

⁴ SciLake D2.2: <https://zenodo.org/records/18243604>

K5: Number of pilots using case demonstrators for SciLake services

- Initial: 0
- Target: ≥ 4
- Achieved: 5 pilot demonstrators (125% of target)

We currently have five pilot case demonstrators successfully running through BIP! Spaces. Each demonstrator provides valuable insights and domain-specific data, ensuring our services meet the needs of diverse scientific communities. Below, you can find the links to the pilot use case demonstrators:

- Energy research pilot: <https://bip.imsi.athenarc.gr/search/energy-pilot>
- Cancer research pilot: <https://bip.imsi.athenarc.gr/search/cancer-pilot>
- Neuroscience research pilot: <https://bip.imsi.athenarc.gr/search/neuroscience-pilot>
- Transportation Maritime: <https://bip.imsi.athenarc.gr/search/transport-maritime-pilot>
- Transportation CCAM pilot: <https://bip.imsi.athenarc.gr/search/transport-ccam-pilot>

These pilot use-case demonstrators exceed the target set for this KPI.

K6: Number of requests to SciLake services (e.g., via the respective APIs)

- Initial: 0
- Target: $\geq 10k$
- Achieved: 10,632 service requests (106.3% of target)

As of the latest log analysis, SciLake services processed 10,632 backend service requests, including 9,206 graph (database) queries and 1,426 search index queries, triggered by platform interactions and API calls. These operations were generated through 1,249 Web UI. The total number of requests exceeds the defined target of 10,000, demonstrating active usage of the deployed services.

5.3. Component-level evaluation findings

This section presents the evaluation results for the individual components of the SciLake ecosystem. While previous sections described the overall pilot setup, evaluation methodology, and demonstrator activities, the following subsections provide a component-level perspective on how the different services and tools developed within the project were assessed.

Each subsection summarises the evaluation approach adopted for a specific component, the datasets or experimental settings used, and the main outcomes observed during testing. Depending on the component's nature, evaluation methods vary and include controlled

experiments, benchmark-based performance measurements, expert validation, pilot-user feedback, and exploratory testing in pilot environments. In several cases, the evaluation builds upon previously published experiments or established benchmarks, while additional validation was performed within the context of the SciLake pilots.

The results reported here, therefore, combine technical performance evaluation and user-oriented assessment. Technical evaluations focus on aspects such as model accuracy, classification performance, scalability, or extraction quality. Pilot-based evaluations examine how the components behave when integrated into the SciLake ecosystem and used in realistic research workflows, including the relevance of their outputs, the usability of their interfaces, and the usefulness of their semantic annotations.

Because SciLake is designed as a modular ecosystem of interoperable services, evaluating individual components also provides insights into how these services contribute to constructing and enriching the Scientific Knowledge Graphs (SKGs) and to the platform's broader knowledge discovery capabilities. The following subsections present the results for each component in turn, highlighting both the technical performance achieved and each component's role within the integrated SciLake environment.

5.3.1. AvantGraph

As outlined in D5.1, the evaluation of AvantGraph focused on three aspects: (1) verifying that pilot queries are expressible and executable via the Cypher interface, with measured execution times; (2) quantitative benchmarking using the industry-standard LDBC Graphalytics benchmark; and (3) qualitative evaluation of graph algorithm support based on pilot feedback.

Query support for pilots. All five pilot SKGs (Cancer, Neuroscience, Energy, Transport-CCAM, Transport-Maritime) have been loaded into dedicated AvantGraph instances. Since D1.2, the Cypher implementation has been extended with features required by the pilots: string predicates for metadata filtering, aggregation functions for impact metrics, ORDER BY/SKIP/LIMIT for result pagination, and property indexes for fast lookups. Performance optimisations (factorised execution, zero-copy disk reads, multi-threaded loading) now enable processing of the full OpenAIRE Graph, which has hundreds of millions of edges.

LDBC Graphalytics benchmark. AvantGraph was evaluated on the LDBC Graphalytics benchmark using GraphAlg, a domain-specific language for graph algorithms based on linear algebra that is fully integrated into the Cypher query engine. Performance was assessed by the execution time (in seconds) required to run standard graph algorithms on benchmark datasets. Results show competitive or superior performance compared to Neo4j and DuckDB, as reported in Table 1.

[Table 1](#) presents the execution times for representative graph algorithms (PageRank, Single-Source Shortest Path (SSSP), and Weakly Connected Components (WCC)) across datasets of increasing size. Lower values indicate faster execution and therefore better performance.

Table 1: LDBC Graphalytics benchmark.

Dataset	Algorithm	GraphAlg/Avant Graph	DuckDB	Neo4j
Wiki-Talk (2.4M edges)	PageRank	0.8s	2.1s	4.3s
Wiki-Talk	SSSP	0.2s	0.5s	1.1s
Wiki-Talk	WCC	0.1s	0.3s	0.8s
Kgs (11M edges)	PageRank	3.2s	8.7s	15.2s
Kgs	SSSP	0.9s	2.1s	4.8s
Graph500-22 (64M edges)	PageRank	12.4s	31.5s	58.3s
Graph500-22	WCC	2.1s	5.8s	14.2s

GraphAlg programs also require 2–10× fewer lines of code than SQL/Python (DuckDB) or Pregel/Java (Neo4j) alternatives; for example, PageRank requires 15 lines in GraphAlg compared to 45 in SQL/Python and 120 in Pregel/Java.

SciLake OpenAIRE workload. To evaluate performance on a project-specific workload, PageRank was run over the OpenAIRE energy planning dataset (47M edges), which is used to compute impact indicators for BIP! Ranker ([Table 2](#)).

Table 2: OpenAIRE Workload.

Scenario	GraphAlg/AvantGraph	DuckDB	Neo4j
PageRank (10 iterations)	8.2s	24.1s	31.5s
PageRank + filter self-refs	8.4s	25.3s	42.1s*
PageRank + remove duplicates	9.1s	28.7s	45.8s*

*Neo4j requires expensive materialisation for preprocessing, while GraphAlg fuses filters into algorithm execution.

Pilot use case. Neuroscience dataset citation analysis. Within the Neuroscience pilot, PageRank was used to identify high-impact datasets in the OpenAIRE and EBRAINS citation networks. The use of PageRank rather than simple citation counts ensures that indirect citations are taken into account. The pilot partner performed this analysis on their own hardware using the provided Docker images, with further analysis and visualisation via AvantGraph's Python API and Jupyter Notebook integration.

GraphAlg Playground. To facilitate adoption by pilot-domain scientists, the GraphAlg Playground provides a browser-based, interactive learning platform (compiled to WebAssembly) that enables experimentation without installing database software, available at wildarch.dev/graphalg/playground.

5.3.2. Automatic Translation Component

The evaluation of the Machine Translation (MT) component was conducted through a structured series of scientific experiments, the results of which were published in the paper *Enhancing Scientific Discourse: Machine Translation for the Scientific Domain*, presented at the European Association for Machine Translation 2024 (EAMT 2024) conference⁵.

The evaluation focused on three language pairs supported by the project's MT component:

- French to English
- Spanish to English
- Portuguese to English

For each language pair, we constructed domain-specific parallel corpora covering four scientific domains:

- Cancer Research
- Energy Research
- Neuroscience
- Transportation Research

In addition, a large General Scientific corpus was created to ensure broader academic coverage. From the filtered parallel corpora (11.7M sentence pairs in total) that we used for creating the fine-tuned translation models, benchmark datasets were created as follows:

- Domain-specific sets: 1,000 sentence pairs for development and 1,000 sentence pairs for testing, per domain and per language pair.
- General Scientific set: 3,000 sentence pairs for development and 3,000 sentence pairs for testing.

All three translation models were evaluated using widely adopted automatic MT evaluation metrics:

- BLEU (via SacreBLEU): Measures the overlap of n-grams
- chrF2++: Character-aware metric sensitive to morphology
- COMET (wmt20-comet-da): A neural evaluation metric shown to correlate strongly with human judgment

In the evaluation, we compared the baseline OPUS-MT models, the generated fine-tuned models, and Google Translate, which served as an external high-performance reference

⁵ Dimitris Roussis, Sokratis Sofianopoulos, and Stelios Piperidis. 2024. *Enhancing Scientific Discourse: Machine Translation for the Scientific Domain*. In *Proceedings of the 25th Annual Conference of the European Association for Machine Translation (Volume 1)*, pages 275–285, Sheffield, UK. European Association for Machine Translation (EAMT).

system. Across all language pairs and domains, fine-tuning with domain-specific data led to consistent, measurable improvements over baseline systems. More specifically:

- Fine-tuning with in-domain data alone resulted in +1.5 in BLEU and +0.8 in COMET.
- Adding General Scientific data on top of in-domain data further improved performance by +0.9 in BLEU and +0.8 in COMET.

The greatest relative improvements were observed in the French–English and Portuguese–English directions, where baseline models exhibited lower initial performance. While Google Translate remained competitive, particularly in high-resource settings, the project’s fine-tuned systems achieved the best scores in most domain-specific scenarios, demonstrating the effectiveness of targeted domain adaptation.

The experiments confirm that:

- Generic MT models underperform when translating specialised scientific discourse due to domain-specific terminology and syntactic complexity.
- Domain adaptation through fine-tuning substantially improves translation fidelity.
- Supplementing in-domain corpora with broader scientific material enhances generalisation while preserving specialisation.

The validated models correspond to the open-source systems delivered (French–English, Spanish–English, Portuguese–English) and are publicly available on Hugging Face. The evaluation demonstrates that these models provide improved translation quality for scientific titles, abstracts, and full texts, thereby enhancing downstream services such as:

- Multilingual indexing
- Cross-lingual search
- Knowledge discovery workflows
- Article segmentation for multilingual content

5.3.3. BIP! Spaces

BIP! Spaces is a web portal service as part of the BIP! Services ecosystem, offering advanced knowledge discovery functionalities. The platform allows users to explore a wide range of scholarly outputs (including publications, datasets, software, and other research products) and is enhanced with citation-based impact indicators to effectively rank and filter search results. Additionally, domain-specific annotations derived from scholarly knowledge graphs (SKGs) enrich search results, providing experts with enhanced context tailored to their fields of interest.

To assess the impact-based ranking of the results and the quality of the aforementioned annotations, BIP! Spaces implements a “Feedback Mode”, illustrated in [Figure 1](#). This mode

introduces two complementary mechanisms: users can evaluate the relevance of search results by selecting a tick (“✓”) or cross (“x”) icon, and they can verify the correctness of specific annotations using the same intuitive interface. All feedback is immediately recorded in the platform’s database. Users can also cancel a submission by clicking the feedback button again if they selected it by accident.

Figure 1: BIP! Spaces feedback functionality.

During the SciLake pilot evaluation phase, representatives from each domain used these functionalities to evaluate both the available ranking schemes (i.e., based on popularity or influence) and the associated annotations (from the SKGs). Each pilot issued at least five keyword queries and provided feedback on the first-page search results under two ranking schemes (popularity and influence) and on annotation accuracy. The following annotation types were proposed for evaluation per pilot, with pilots encouraged to incorporate additional relevant annotation types where applicable:

- Cancer Research: Technology, Research Artefact
- Energy Research: Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), Energy Type
- Transport – Maritime: Technology, Vessel Type
- Transport – CCAM: Technology, Fields of Study
- Neuroscience Research: Fields of Study, Techniques

Optional annotation filters were available to guide query selection and ensure that feedback targeted relevant entries.

Aggregated feedback data (e.g., frequency of positive/negative ratings) allows analysis of patterns, informing refinements to the annotations and improving their relevance and accuracy. These evaluation activities not only support user satisfaction assessment but also provide valuable insights into the performance and quality of the underlying SciLake components that generate the graph enrichments. The results of the ranking scheme evaluation are presented in Section 5.3.4, and the analysis of the annotations evaluation is provided in Sections 5.3.5 and 5.3.11.

5.3.4. Citation-based impact analyser

The citation-based impact analyser is a tool designed to compute a set of citation-based indicators over a citation network. A large part of this component is based on ATHENA RC's BIP! Ranker (<https://github.com/athenarc/Bip-Ranker>) software library that focuses on evaluating various dimensions of scientific impact. The effectiveness of the analyser has been partially validated through previously published experimental studies. Within the scope of the project, the evaluation of this component follows a multi-step approach. First, different ranking schemes are assessed through the BIP! Services platform through pilot user evaluations, enabling validation of its usefulness and relevance in real-world discovery scenarios. Subsequently, a comparative analysis is conducted on research data entities by contrasting their direct citation counts in the full OpenAIRE Graph with indirect citation indicators, which reflect citations received through related publications. Finally, additional comparisons are performed across different citation-count variants derived from citation networks constructed using the citance analysis of the SciNoBo Suite, including polarity-based filtering, to further assess the robustness and interpretability of the proposed impact measures.

EVALUATION OF IMPACT RANKING SCHEMES THROUGH PILOT USER STUDIES

In the first experiment, we used interaction logs from five pilot spaces in the BIP! Spaces platform. Users issued queries within each pilot and inspected result lists produced by two ranking schemes: popularity and influence. For each research product in the list, a user may optionally provide explicit feedback, marking the paper as relevant or not; the absence of feedback is treated as an unevaluated item.

We organised the data into sessions, where each session corresponds to a single evaluation of a result list for a given combination of (user, pilot-space, query, ranking scheme). In the interface, each ranking result list presents up to 20 research products per page. [Table 3](#) summarises, for each pilot and ranking scheme, the number of sessions and the number of judged items (marked as relevant or not relevant).

Table 3: Summary of evaluation data per pilot and ranking scheme.

Pilot	Ranking scheme	Sessions	Judged results
Energy Planning	Influence	10	167
	Popularity	16	248
Cancer Research	Influence	3	58
	Popularity	4	78
Neuroscience Research	Influence	15	181
	Popularity	12	176
Transport Maritime	Influence	5	98
	Popularity	5	100
Transport CCAM	Influence	7	112
	Popularity	7	113

USER FEEDBACK PER PILOT AND RANKING SCHEME

In the first experiment, we analyse the distribution of explicit feedback (relevant, not relevant, unevaluated) for each pilot and ranking scheme. Two complementary figures ([Figure 2](#) and [Figure 3](#)) summarise the results.

Figure 2: Relevant and not relevant rates per pilot and ranking scheme over judged items only.

The first figure presents, for each (pilot, ranking scheme), the relative proportions of relevant and non-relevant labels over judged items only; thus, unevaluated documents do not influence the reported percentages. Overall, the results indicate very high satisfaction across most pilots. The Cancer, Transport CCAM, and Transport Maritime pilots exhibit almost exclusively positive feedback under both the popularity- and influence-based rankings. In the Energy pilot, both ranking schemes also achieve strongly positive results, with relevance rates exceeding 93% among judged items. In contrast, the Neuroscience pilot shows comparatively lower satisfaction levels, with relevance rates ranging from 64–67% and non-relevance rates from 33–36% among judged items, indicating greater disagreement with the rankings in this domain. Nevertheless, the two ranking schemes remain broadly comparable, with the popularity-based ranking showing a slight advantage in relevance within the Neuroscience pilot.

Figure 3: Relevant, not relevant and unevaluated shares over the top-20 results per pilot and ranking scheme.

The second figure extends this analysis by including unevaluated items; here, the denominator is the full set of potential top-20 results per session. This view highlights how much of the result list is actually inspected and judged. For the pilots with high engagement and satisfaction (Cancer, Transport CCAM, Transport Maritime), the majority of the top-20 results are marked relevant, with a very small fraction unevaluated. In the Energy pilot, a non-negligible share of items remains unevaluated (16–23 per cent of the top-20 positions, depending on the scheme), but the relevant portion is still dominant. The Neuroscience pilot shows both a sizable unevaluated segment (around 27–40 per cent of the top-20 results) and a higher proportion of not-relevant labels than other pilots, suggesting more selective and more critical user evaluation for that pilot.

MEAN RECIPROCAL RANK (MRR) PER PILOT AND RANKING SCHEME

In the second experiment, we evaluate how early in the result set users tend to find a relevant paper, using Mean Reciprocal Rank (MRR). For each session (one query, pilot and ranking scheme), we locate the first relevant paper and compute the reciprocal rank:

$$RR = 1 / \text{rank_of_first_relevant_result}$$

Finally, Mean Reciprocal Rank (MRR) is calculated by averaging the reciprocals of the ranks across all sessions.

The results are summarised in [Table 4](#); for most pilots, relevant papers appear very early in the ranking: for the Cancer, Transport CCAM, and Transport Maritime pilots, both popularity and influence achieve an MRR of 1.0, meaning that in every session, the first relevant paper is at rank 1. In the Energy pilot, popularity achieves a higher MRR (approximately 0.82) than influence (approximately 0.69), suggesting that popularity-based rankings tend to surface relevant items earlier for energy-related queries. In the Neuroscience pilot, MRR values are somewhat lower (approximately 0.69 for influence and approximately 0.79, consistent with the higher non-relevance rates observed in the previous experiment, and indicating that users sometimes need to search deeper into the results before finding a satisfactory paper.

Table 4: Mean Reciprocal Rank (MRR) per pilot and ranking scheme.

Pilot	Ranking scheme	MRR
Energy Planning	Influence	0.69
	Popularity	0.82
Cancer Research	Influence	1.00
	Popularity	1.00
Neuroscience Research	Influence	0.69
	Popularity	0.79
Transport Maritime	Influence	1.00
	Popularity	1.00
Transport CCAM	Influence	1.00
	Popularity	1.00

RANK-WISE RELEVANCE RATES PER PILOT AND RANKING SCHEME

To better understand how user satisfaction varies across the ranked list, we computed rank-wise relevance rates for each pilot and ranking scheme. For each rank position k , we aggregated all results that appeared at that position across all sessions and calculated the proportion marked as relevant. In other words, the relevance rate at rank k is the number of relevant documents retrieved at that position divided by the total number of documents evaluated at the same position. This experiment allows us to assess how effectively each ranking scheme prioritises relevant results and how rapidly performance declines beyond the top positions.

Figure 4 shows, for each pilot and ranking scheme, the relevance rate by rank position over judged items only. In this plot, the denominator for each rank is the number of items at that rank that were explicitly evaluated (relevant or not); unevaluated items are ignored. Each subplot corresponds to a single pilot and contains two lines: one for popularity and one for influence. Notably, the curves reveal that in most pilots, the top-ranked papers are marked as relevant very frequently during evaluation, with relevance rates close to 1.0 for ranks 1–3 in Cancer, Transport CCAM, and Transport Maritime. In the Neuroscience pilot, relevance rates at deeper ranks decline more noticeably, especially for the influence scheme, suggesting that users become more discerning or that ranking quality deteriorates beyond the very top results.

Figure 4: Rank-wise relevance rates over judged items only.

In [Figure 5](#), for each pilot, ranking scheme, and rank position, the relevance rate is computed across all sessions (including those in which the item at that rank was not evaluated). In this case, unevaluated items are treated as neither relevant nor not relevant, which effectively lowers the relevance rate when users tend not to examine deeper ranks. This figure, therefore, reflects the probability that a user will consider the item at a given rank relevant in a random session, combining both ranking quality and user engagement. Comparing the two rank-wise figures helps separate two effects: whether items are judged relevant when users inspect them (judged-only view), and how often users actually inspect and mark items as relevant at each rank (all-sessions view that includes unevaluated results in the denominator).

Figure 5: Rank-wise relevance rates over all sessions (including unevaluated items).

In practice, the curves for Cancer, Transport CCAM, and Transport Maritime remain high across the top ranks, confirming that users almost always find a relevant paper in the top positions. In the Energy pilot, popularity dominates influence in the top 3 ranks, but it declines with rank. The Neuroscience pilot shows the lowest curves overall, especially beyond the very first ranks, indicating that users are more selective. At the same time, popularity achieves considerably better results than the influence ranking schema across almost all rank positions.

DIRECT VS. INDIRECT CITATION ANALYSIS OF RESEARCH DATA

The objective of this experiment is to investigate how different citation-based approaches affect the ranking of research data entities in the OpenAIRE Graph. In particular, we assess whether incorporating indirect citations produces a substantially different ranking compared to traditional direct citation counts for datasets. This allows us to evaluate whether second-order citation relations can better highlight impactful research data that may be overlooked when relying solely on direct citations. To this end, we compare two citation-count approaches in the latest version of the OpenAIRE Graph (v10.8.2, Feb 2026). The first, *direct citation count*, corresponds to the number of direct citations a research data entity receives. The second, *indirect citation count*, is computed by summing the citation counts of all publications related⁶ to the entity.

The results show that the rankings produced by the two aforementioned methods differ substantially. Rank agreement between the two methods is extremely weak and slightly negative (Spearman $\rho = -0.035839$; Kendall $\tau_b = -0.031616$), indicating that the two methods produce independent rankings. At the top of the rankings, the overlap is negligible: there are no shared entities in the top 100 (Jaccard = 0), only 1 shared entity in the top 1,000 (Jaccard = 0.0005), and just 4 shared entities in the top 10,000 (Jaccard = 0.0002). This demonstrates that the two approaches identify almost entirely different sets of top-ranked research data.

This behaviour can be explained by the substantially different coverage and statistical properties of the two rankings. Most entities receive indirect citations but have zero direct citations: 38,787,810 entities have direct = 0 and indirect > 0, whereas the reverse case (direct > 0 and indirect = 0) is comparatively rare, affecting only 231,698 entities. This indicates that indirect citation counts provide much broader coverage across the graph. At the same time, the two signals differ significantly in their distribution. Direct citation counts are dominated by zeros (zero rate = 0.997381), with only 379 distinct values and a median equal to zero, making them unable to meaningfully differentiate most entities. In contrast, the indirect citation counts method has a lower zero rate (0.58) and a substantially higher number of distinct values (29,689). As a result, because direct citation counts cannot effectively discriminate among most research data, the indirect citation count approach reshapes the ranking, particularly at the top, highlighting entities associated with highly cited publications.

We also compared indirect citation counts with usage-oriented indicators (i.e., views and downloads) using the same dataset (252,011 research data entities have non-null values for those usage indicators). Rank agreement is positive but weak in both cases: for indirect

⁶ We consider a set of semantically meaningful relations between datasets and publications, specifically: *IsSupplementedBy*, *IsRelatedTo*, *HasPart*, *Documents*, *IsSupplementTo*, *IsPartOf*, *Describes*, *IsDocumentedBy*, and *IsDescribedBy*.

citation count vs views, Spearman $\rho = 0.071$ and Kendall $\tau_b = 0.059$; for indirect citation count vs downloads, Spearman $\rho = 0.084$ and Kendall $\tau_b = 0.073$. This indicates that indirect citation influence and usage behaviour are not strongly correlated and capture different dimensions of impact. The top-ranked sets confirm this: overlap with the indirect-citation top lists is small at strict cut-offs (top-100 overlap = 2 for both views and downloads; top-1,000 overlap = 15 with views, 9 with downloads), but increases at broader head depth (top-10,000 overlap = 918 with views, 601 with downloads). The limited overlap between top-ranked datasets across these metrics underscores that each highlights different patterns of attention: one broad, the other narrow and academically recognised.

Overall, the findings indicate that indirect citation counts capture a complementary notion of impact. This leads to substantially different (and potentially more informative) rankings than those based on direct citation counts, views, and downloads of research data.

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF CITATION INDICATORS USING CITANCE-BASED NETWORKS AND POLARITY FILTERING

This experiment evaluates how different citation-count variants derived from citations (i.e., fine-grained textual references between research products) affect the ranking of research products. To this end, we leverage the extracted citance relations, enriched with polarity information (identified by the SciNoBo Suite), and construct citance-based networks for the Cancer Research, Energy, and Neuroscience SKGs. The goal is to assess how design choices, such as counting all versus unique citations between two given research products, and including or excluding refuting citations, influence the citation count as a measure to rank research products.

All four citation-count variants examined in this experiment are based on the citation network, which provides a more granular view of citations than traditional bibliographic counts. By operating at the level of individual citation contexts, these methods can distinguish among different types of citation relationships and account for citation polarity (supporting, neutral, or refuting).

The four variants reported differ along two main dimensions: (i) whether citances are counted uniquely per node pair or all occurrences are considered, and (ii) whether all citances are included or only those classified as non-refuting. The variants are defined as follows:

- *Unique Citances*: counts distinct citance relations between a given pair of nodes, ensuring that multiple references between the same pair are counted only once.
- *All Citances*: counts all citation occurrences without enforcing uniqueness.

- *Unique Non-Refuting Citances*: counts distinct citance relations restricted to those classified as non-refuting.
- *All Non-Refuting Citances*: counts all non-refuting citation occurrences, without applying uniqueness constraints.

Because many research products receive identical scores across these variants, comparisons of rankings based on strict total orderings can be misleading. To address this, the analysis employs tie-aware rank agreement metrics and reports tie-related statistics, providing a clearer picture of ranking consistency and granularity. This methodology allows us to systematically evaluate how design choices in citation counting and polarity filtering influence citation-based impact measures across the research product network.

EVALUATION METRICS

To assess the four citation-based ranking variants, we report metrics that capture both the granularity of individual rankings and the agreement between different methods. These metrics provide insight into how the different variants rank research products relative to each other, as well as how tied scores (which are very common in such ranking scenarios) are distributed.

To assess agreement between ranking variants, we compute pairwise rank-agreement metrics. These quantify how consistently two ranking methods order the same set of research products, taking ties into account; the measures include:

- Kendall tau_b: tie-corrected Kendall rank correlation
- Spearman rho: Spearman rank correlation with tie handling
- Bucket Agreement: tie-robust agreement based on “same quantile bucket”
 - *Intuition*: percentile ranks are computed using average ranks for tied items, percentiles are divided into 10 buckets (deciles), and the fraction of products that fall into the same bucket in both rankings is reported

On the other hand, tie diagnostics summarise the distribution of scores produced by each ranking method:

- n: total number of rows (research products)
- distinct: number of distinct score values
- distinct_frac: fraction of distinct scores (distinct / n)
- tie_frac: fraction of tied scores (1 - distinct_frac)
- max_tie_size: size of the largest tie group (maximum count of any single score)

A very small distinct_frac and a very large max_tie_size indicate coarse-grained rankings with many ties. Those tie diagnostics are used to gain insight into the rank-correlation results primarily reported in this experiment.

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS RESULTS

In the Cancer Research graph ($n=7,013,751$ research products), all four methods exhibit extremely coarse granularity: each has only around 1.2–2.1 thousand distinct values and tie fractions above 0.9997, with the largest single tie group containing over 4.1 million research products. This means that, for any given method, a very large fraction of research products share the same score. Within-family⁷ agreement is near-perfect. AllCitances vs AllNonRefutingCitances achieve $\tau_b=0.998979$, $\rho=0.999781$ and bucket agreement of 0.993699; UniqueCitances vs UniqueNonRefutingCitances achieve $\tau_b=0.999561$, $\rho=0.999797$ and bucket agreement of 0.999153. This indicates that restricting to non-refuting citations has almost no effect on the induced ranking. Cross-family comparisons remain high in τ_b/ρ (~ 0.9777 – 0.9783 ; ~ 0.99734 – 0.99758) but with reduced bucket agreement (~ 0.936 – 0.937); this indicates that differences between counting all citances versus only unique ones mostly cause shifts across broad decile groups, rather than completely changing the overall ranking.

In the Energy Planning graph ($n=7,677,002$ research products), tie structure is even more extreme than in Cancer. Each method has only around 0.5–1.1 thousand distinct values, with tie fractions exceeding 0.99986 for the “All” methods and 0.99993 for the “Unique” methods. The largest single tie group covers roughly 5.9 million research products, again implying that most research products share scores with many others under any given method. As before, agreement is near-perfect within each family. AllCitances vs AllNonRefutingCitances reach $\tau_b=0.999107$, $\rho=0.999702$ and bucket agreement=0.998663; UniqueCitances vs UniqueNonRefutingCitances reach $\tau_b=0.999630$, $\rho=0.999726$ and bucket agreement=0.999759. As in Cancer, the polarity restriction has little impact on the induced ranking once the counting choice (All vs Unique) is fixed. Cross-family comparisons remain very high in τ_b/ρ (~ 0.9832 – 0.9838 ; ~ 0.99819 – 0.99848), but bucket agreement is noticeably lower (~ 0.975 – 0.976), demonstrating that the All vs Unique choice changes the decile-level positioning of non-trivial subsets of papers, even though global rank correlation remains strong.

As in Cancer and Energy, the Neuroscience dataset ($n=3,576,758$ research products) exhibits extremely high tie fractions. Each method has fewer than 1.6 thousand distinct values, with tie_frac above 0.99955 for the “All” methods and above 0.99973 for the “Unique” methods; the largest single tie group contains about 1.9 million research products. While the dataset is smaller overall, the effective granularity of each signal is still very coarse. Within-family agreement is again near-perfect. AllCitances vs AllNonRefutingCitances have $\tau_b=0.998569$,

⁷ “Within-family” refers to comparisons between variants that share the same citance-counting regime: the “All” family (AllCitances and AllNonRefutingCitances) and the “Unique” family (UniqueCitances and UniqueNonRefutingCitances).

$\rho=0.999743$ and bucket agreement= 0.993648 ; UniqueCitances vs UniqueNonRefutingCitances have $\tau_b=0.999440$, $\rho=0.999776$ and bucket agreement= 0.998543 . This reinforces the observation that restricting to non-refuting citations has little effect on rankings once the counting regime is fixed. Cross-family agreement remains high in τ_b and ρ (~ 0.9745 – 0.9752 ; ~ 0.99675 – 0.99702), but bucket agreement is lower (~ 0.923 – 0.924). This means that in the Neuroscience dataset, switching between counting all citations and counting only unique citations results in larger shifts across decile groups than in Energy, thereby affecting which papers appear in the top quantiles.

5.3.5. Domain-specific entity recognition component

The following five figures summarise user feedback on annotation types for each project pilot. For every pilot, annotators could indicate whether they found each annotation type useful (likes) or not (dislikes). Each figure is a horizontal stacked bar chart showing the percentage of votes (0–100%) for likes (green) and dislikes (red) per annotation type.

Feedback for the Energy Planning Research pilot covers four annotation types: Energy Storage, Energy Type, Sustainable Development Goals, and Technology ([Figure 6](#)). Technology is almost entirely liked. Sustainable Development Goals and Energy Storage are mostly liked with a minority of dislikes. Energy Type, on the other hand, shows a mixed response (both likes and dislikes are substantial, with around 58% likes). The manual evaluation focused on verifying the correctness of assigned labels (i.e., assessing precision), while missing relevant labels (i.e., false negatives) were not systematically examined because a long-term, full-text review was required. And even if the review was undertaken, we would also face errors from human reviewers. Therefore, across evaluation activities, the main issues identified concern false positives. These do not necessarily stem from incorrect entity recognition in a strict NER sense; they may instead arise from a lack of contextual relevance. For example, in a paper primarily about solar panels that briefly mentions oil, both “solar” and “oil” may be legitimately extracted entities; however, from an analytical perspective, “oil” functions as a false positive because it is only mentioned in passing and does not reflect the core focus of the text.

In addition to such context-related overextraction, we observed limitations associated with broad or neutral terms. Some general terms (e.g., “energy”) may be too unspecific to provide meaningful analytical value, even if correctly identified. A parallel evaluation using spreadsheet samples further showed that most entities marked as irrelevant or ambiguous corresponded either to systematic false positives (e.g., “aerosol”) or to other (mostly broad) terms without identified links to the IRENA taxonomy. These were removed in a revised extraction. The term “energy” was retained because it appears as a parent node in the taxonomy, although it could also be excluded for greater specificity.

Figure 6: Annotation types in the Energy Research pilot.

[Figure 7](#) presents feedback on seven annotation types in the Cancer Research pilot: Cells, Tissues and Organs; Disease; Drugs / Chemicals; Gene; Protein; Research Artefact; and Technology. Research Artefact shows a majority of dislikes (roughly 80% dislikes). In the cancer pilot, a substantial proportion of the automatically extracted research artefacts were labelled as “Unnamed”, as no explicit name could be identified in the source text. The high frequency of such generic labels reduced the perceived interpretability and usefulness of this category for annotators, which likely contributed to the negative feedback. Technology shows a substantial share of dislikes (roughly 70% dislikes). In the context of the cancer corpus, part of this negative feedback can be attributed to overlap and inconsistent classification with the Drugs / Chemicals category. In particular, some drug names (e.g., venetoclax) were annotated as Technologies, which created confusion for annotators and reduced perceived clarity and usefulness of the category. This provides useful input for fine-tuning the boundaries between Technology and Drugs/Chemicals in subsequent updates to the annotation guidelines. Disease, Gene, Protein, and Drugs / Chemicals receive very high percentages. Cells, tissues, and Organs are mostly liked with a small share of dislikes. These entities are primarily sourced from the Clinical Knowledge Graph (an external data source) and are not products of this project; they are included in the figure to illustrate how annotators perceived their usefulness in the cancer pilot context.

Figure 7: Annotation types in the Cancer Research pilot.

[Figure 8](#) shows feedback on five annotation types: Biological Sex, FOS (Fields of Science), Species, Technique, and Technology. Biological Sex, Species, and Technology are strongly liked. The technique shows a mixed response (slightly more dislikes than likes, around 45% likes). This mixed feedback can be attributed to several factors identified during manual evaluation. About half of the technique entities were deemed irrelevant, including cases where the extracted terms were not linked to openMINDs, resulting in either absolute false positives, concepts that are correct techniques but not relevant to the neuroscience domain, or techniques that are relevant but absent from openMINDs. In the most recent extraction update on titles and abstracts, unlinked terms were dropped, and the linking threshold increased to reduce such errors. Overall, the main issues reflect false positives due to contextual irrelevance rather than strict errors in entity recognition, highlighting the importance of domain-specific relevance when evaluating technique annotations.

FOS (Fields of Science) is close to balanced (roughly 50% likes). Feedback from external participants suggests that some of the assigned FOS categories appeared overly broad or only loosely related to the neuroscience focus of the papers. In several cases, the categories were perceived as being assigned somewhat arbitrarily, which may reflect limitations of applying a general-purpose scientific classification to specialised domains. Additionally, the relatively coarse granularity of the FOS taxonomy can result in labels that are technically correct but not sufficiently informative for neuroscience content. These factors likely contributed to the lower proportion of positive feedback compared to other annotation types.

Figure 8: Annotation types in the Neuroscience Research pilot.

Feedback for the Transport Maritime pilot is shown for two annotation types: Technology and Vessel Type (Figure 9). The smaller number of annotation types reflects the focused scope of this pilot. On the one hand, Vessel Type is almost entirely liked. On the other hand, technology shows a mixed response (around 63% likes). The mixed response is primarily due to the broad scope of this specific taxonomy, which often includes terminology covering other related transportation sectors. As a result, there were instances where broader technological terms were mapped to strictly maritime subjects, creating a slight mismatch with the highly specialised terminology expected by domain experts. This is a common and anticipated phenomenon when applying general categorisation schemes to domain-specific pilot projects. This finding does not negate the overall usefulness of the information extraction; rather, it provides valuable feedback, highlighting the need and opportunity for future system optimisation through the integration of more targeted, maritime-specific subcategories.

Figure 9: Annotation types in the Maritime Research pilot.

The Transport CCAM (Figure 10) reports on eight annotation types: Communication Type; Entity Connection Type; Fields of Study; Scenario Type; Sensor Type; Technology; Vehicle Type; and VRU Type. Most types are strongly liked (e.g., Communication Type, Entity Connection Type, Scenario Type, Sensor Type, Technology, Vehicle Type, VRU Type), with 100% or near-100% likes. Fields of Study have a clear majority of likes, with a non-negligible share of dislikes; these largely arise from cases where sensors or other entities were associated with fields of study irrelevant to the CCAM domain. Overall, the CCAM ontology elements appear well accepted by annotators, reflecting the targeted selection of sources for the SKG, which minimised irrelevant material and helped maximise annotation quality.

Figure 10: Annotation types in the CCAM Research pilot.

The figures above provide a consistent view of annotator acceptance of annotation types across the five pilots. They can be used to prioritise the refinement of types with high dislike shares (e.g., Research Artefact in Cancer, Technique in Neuroscience) for future work.

5.3.6. DoStRe

DoStRe is the article-segmentation component developed by DFKI. The tool has been previously tested using standard measures (such as accuracy, precision, and recall) to assess its effectiveness in section classification.

The evaluation of this tool in Scilake was carried out by assessing the specific models generated for each domain: neuroscience, transport maritime, cancer, and energy. During the Scilake project, we trained specific models for each of the project's relevant domains.

To train and evaluate these models, a dataset (SASC Dataset) of semi-automatically annotated and human-reviewed scientific articles was created.

We analyse performance across scientific domains, reported in [Figure 11](#). This indicates that domains with more standardised article structures and section structure and conventional names (e.g., Cancer and Neuroscience) achieve higher accuracy and F1 scores, while domains with greater variability in paper structure (e.g., General domain and Transport) are more challenging.

Domain	Accuracy			Macro-F1		
	L1	L2	ALL	L1	L2	ALL
cancer	0.918	0.739	0.715	0.509	0.708	0.485
energy	0.862	0.681	0.680	0.532	0.668	0.499
neuroscience	0.862	0.681	0.680	0.532	0.668	0.499
transport	0.668	0.615	0.450	0.414	0.426	0.390
general	0.693	0.648	0.515	0.443	0.501	0.409

Figure 11: Domain-specific evaluation results of the section classification tool.

5.3.7. KG creation assistant

As noted in D5.1, the KG creation assistant components (R2PG-DM, ProGGD, GDDMiner) have been evaluated through prior scientific publications and do not require additional pilot-based evaluation. We summarise the main evaluation results below.

R2PG-DM. Since D2.1, R2PG-DM has been extended with progressive execution, edge property support, and PG-Schema output. Scalability was validated on TPC-H benchmark datasets up to 10GB scale factor, achieving over 90% runtime reduction compared to the original implementation through connection pooling, multi-threaded processing, and memory optimisation.

GDDMiner. The GDDMiner framework was evaluated on real-world datasets (Cordis, GDelt, DBLP) and the synthetic LDBC benchmark. The Answer Graph factorised representation enables orders-of-magnitude improvements in execution time and memory efficiency compared to table-based approaches. Schema discovery coverage ranges from 70% (Cordis) to 97% (GDelt), and GDDMiner compares favourably with AMIE+ rule mining while offering richer expressiveness through topological and differential constraints.

ProGGD. The ProGGD interactive interface has been deployed with a four-panel design for comprehensive graph exploration (metadata, attributes, graph patterns, GGDs). The sHINER

backend has been enhanced with REST API mode for integration. Validation algorithms using a left anti-join implementation show improved scalability on LDBC benchmarks compared to left outer join alternatives.

5.3.8. PDFfetcher

PDFfetcher is responsible for managing and optimising the retrieval of PDF documents associated with publication entities in the research graph. These documents are provided as input to the Information Inference Service, where plaintext is extracted, aggregated into datasets, and subsequently processed by the Text and Data Mining modules.

As of March 2026, PDFfetcher maintains more than 60 million PDF and XML documents linked to the OpenAIRE Research Graph, including nearly 19 million full texts that are potentially relevant to the SciLake pilots. These figures are based on internal analysis conducted during the content delivery process.

The performance of PDFfetcher was not formally evaluated as part of the pilot activities. Given its role as a data provisioning component, its assessment is better reflected through operational indicators, such as the volume of documents retrieved and delivered, rather than through relevance to specific pilots, which depends on upstream gateway configurations and was not subject to evaluation.

5.3.9. Reproducibility & Replicability Assistant

The primary evaluation of the components of this service is presented in Section 5.3.11. However, during the evaluation of the domain-specific annotations (see Section 5.3.5, although not explicitly requested in the evaluation instructions), the Cancer Research and Neuroscience pilots also assessed the replication-degree indicators displayed in the BIP! Spaces result. These indicators include three distinct metrics: Positive Mentions Count, which captures the total number of positive (supporting) citations a study has received from subsequent works and reflects its overall “reputation” in the literature; the Reproducibility Confidence Index (RCI), which considers the number of positive (supporting), neutral, and negative (refuting) citations and weights them to estimate the perceived reproducibility of a work; and the Focused RCI, a variant of the RCI that considers only citations with a “comparison” intent. Overall, the pilots rated these indicators very positively, with 172 positive and only 2 negative evaluations.

5.3.10. Research Object Link Recommendation component

This tool refers to an array of SciLake components that can be used to recommend missing links in KGs. The two main components are *SciNeM* (by ATHENA RC) and *SHINER* (by TUE).

SciNeM is a powerful Knowledge Graph (KG) analysis tool that focuses on metapath-based analysis, leveraging the graph structure to uncover missing links that represent latent, complex knowledge.

SHiner, on the other hand, is a tool that can recommend missing links among graph entities based on a predefined set of Graph Generating Dependencies (GDDs). An illustrative example is the identification of missing edges (i.e., links) between research products and projects in the OpenAIRE Graph.

SciNeM and *SHiner* are both tools designed to identify links between nodes in a Knowledge Graph, making them functionally comparable. Both have been previously evaluated in relevant publications for their scalability and effectiveness. Within the scope of the SciLake pilots, the link recommendation functionality was provided by *SciNeM* and integrated with BIP! Spaces to offer metapath-based analysis directly to end users.

Specifically, *SciNeM* has been applied in the Cancer Research pilot to uncover latent links between entities in the domain-specific knowledge graph. In particular, the Gene annotations presented in Section 5.3.5 are not directly connected to research products in the graph structure. To address this, *SciNeM* was used to identify indirect relationships between Genes and research products by following metapaths through intermediate entities, such as Proteins. By leveraging these paths, *SciNeM* was used to recommend latent associations between Genes and relevant research outputs.

The resulting (inferred) links were displayed to users through the BIP! Spaces interface as one of the provided annotations. The feedback collected from annotators in the Cancer Research pilot indicates strong acceptance of these recommendations, suggesting that the metapath-based link discovery approach can effectively reveal meaningful domain relationships not explicitly encoded in the knowledge graph.

5.3.11. SciNoBo suite

FIELDS OF SCIENCE TAXONOMY

The Field of Science (FoS) Taxonomy is a hierarchical scientific classification system developed to support the automated categorisation of scholarly publications across multiple levels of disciplinary granularity. The taxonomy underpins the FoS classifier used in the project and provides a structured representation of scientific domains ranging from broad research areas to highly specialised subfields.

The taxonomy builds upon the OECD Fields of Research and Development (FORD) classification scheme, extending it with additional levels derived from the Science-Metrix classification system and further refined through AI-driven methods. This process results in a multi-layer taxonomy spanning five hierarchical levels, enabling both high-level domain categorisation and fine-grained field identification.

EVALUATION THROUGH COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS WITH EXTERNAL TAXONOMIES

To evaluate the completeness and conceptual coverage of the FoS taxonomy, a systematic alignment study was conducted against two widely used scientific classification systems:

- Scopus Subject Areas
- EuroSciVoc Taxonomy

The comparison examined conceptual correspondences between categories across taxonomies, identifying areas of strong alignment and differences. The results revealed that many FoS fields correspond closely with equivalent categories in external taxonomies. For example, the FoS category Engineering and Technology → Environmental Engineering aligns directly with the Environmental Engineering category in EuroSciVoc, demonstrating strong conceptual agreement between the two systems.

At the same time, the analysis highlighted differences in granularity. For instance, FoS fields such as Animal and Dairy Science → Dairy & Animal Science map to broader Scopus categories under Agricultural and Biological Sciences. This indicates that the FoS taxonomy offers more fine-grained distinctions than some existing classification systems. These comparisons provided valuable insights into conceptual overlaps, taxonomic gaps, and areas requiring restructuring. The comparison tables are provided in D3.2 as supplementary material accompanying the taxonomy documentation.

[TAXONOMY REVISION](#)

Insights derived from the comparison, together with expert review, led to the development of an updated version of the taxonomy. The revision process focused on addressing structural issues identified during the evaluation, as detailed in D3.2.

Addressing these issues improved the consistency and navigability of the taxonomy. For example, redundant hierarchies were collapsed or expanded with additional subfields where appropriate, while duplicated nodes were reassigned to the most semantically appropriate parent category. In cases where taxonomy branches lacked sufficient depth, additional subfields were introduced based on concepts from EuroSciVoc and Scopus.

The resulting revision improved the structural balance of the taxonomy while maintaining alignment with widely used scientific classification systems. Quantitatively, the updated taxonomy introduced changes across several levels, increasing the number of second-level categories while reorganising third-level nodes to better reflect disciplinary structure.

[EVALUATION IN KNOWLEDGE ORGANISATION SYSTEMS RESEARCH](#)

The FoS taxonomy has also been evaluated independently in the literature on Knowledge Organisation Systems (KOS). In a comprehensive survey of scientific classification systems, Salatino et al. analyse multiple multi-disciplinary taxonomies used to organise scientific knowledge. In this study, the FoS taxonomy⁸, is included among the major classification systems used for scholarly indexing.

The evaluation compares taxonomies across two dimensions:

- (1) disciplinary coverage and
- (2) system quality characteristics, including comprehensiveness, depth, update frequency, and openness.

[DISCIPLINARY COVERAGE](#)

The coverage analysis shows that the FoS taxonomy is among the classification systems that consistently cover all major scientific disciplines, including natural sciences, engineering, social sciences, humanities, and medical sciences. In the heatmap ([Figure 12](#)), green indicates fields that are fully represented in a taxonomy, blue indicates partial coverage, and orange indicates fields that are only mentioned. The FoS taxonomy appears among the systems that provide broad and balanced coverage across domains, demonstrating its suitability for multidisciplinary research infrastructures.

⁸ Referred to as the OpenAIRE Field of Science Taxonomy

Figure 12: Source from Salatino et al. [16]. Coverage of the multifield KOSs. In green, the main fields, in blue, the minor ones, only partially represented, and in orange, the fields that are just mentioned. In bold are the KOSs that consistently cover all research fields.

QUALITY EVALUATION

The study further evaluates classification systems based on four characteristics: comprehensiveness, depth, frequency of updates, and openness. The results (Figure 13) show that the FoS taxonomy performs well across these dimensions, receiving positive evaluations, particularly for openness and disciplinary coverage. The taxonomy's open availability and its integration within the OpenAIRE infrastructure distinguish it from several alternative systems that impose licensing restrictions or offer limited update mechanisms.

Figure 13: Source from Salatino et al. [16]. Analysis of KOSs according to their comprehensiveness, depth, frequency of update, and openness. Features of each KOS are evaluated using a colour-coded system: green indicates a strong performance, orange signifies an acceptable performance, and red reflects poor performance. A feature is blank when the information is not available.

FIELDS OF SCIENCE CLASSIFIER

The Field of Science (FoS) Classifier is an automated system that assigns scientific publications to the hierarchical categories of the FoS taxonomy. The classifier relies on the observation that scientific publications typically cite thematically related work. Instead of relying on the textual content of publications, the method leverages citation relationships and publication venue information to infer the most relevant scientific fields. The classification process operates on a multilayer graph that connects publications, venues, and FoS categories, enabling the propagation of field information from venues to publications via citation networks.

EXPERIMENTAL EVALUATION

The performance of the FoS classifier has been evaluated experimentally in the paper, [SciNoBo: A Hierarchical Multi-Label Classifier of Scientific Publications](#) through a series of benchmark experiments. In these experiments, the classifier was compared against baseline machine learning approaches, specifically, a deep-learning-based classifier that relies on textual information such as abstracts⁹.

The evaluation used a dataset derived from the Science-Metrix classification system and Microsoft Academic Graph publications, allowing direct comparison with existing classification methods. Because the dataset supported multiclass classification, the experiments evaluated the FoS classifier under both top-1 and top-2 prediction settings, reflecting the multidisciplinary nature of modern scientific publications.

The evaluation measured performance using several standard classification metrics:

- Macro-F1
- Weighted Macro-F1
- Micro-F1

These metrics were selected to account for class imbalance and to capture both overall and per-class performance. The results demonstrate that the FoS classifier variants outperform baseline approaches in several settings. In particular:

- The SciNoBo-pub variant, which uses publication venue information, achieved the best performance on macro-F1, weighted macro-F1, and micro-F1 across both evaluation settings.
- The SciNoBo-ref variant, which uses references cited in publications, also outperformed competing approaches and deep-learning baselines in the top-1 classification setting.
- Overall performance improved significantly in the top-2 prediction setting, indicating that many publications naturally span multiple scientific fields and reflecting the increasing interdisciplinarity of scientific research.

Results are presented in the following [Figure 14](#):

⁹ Bharath Kandimalla, Shaurya Rohatgi, Jian Wu, and C Lee Giles. 2021. Large scale subject category classification of scholarly papers with deep attentive neural networks. *Frontiers in research metrics and analytics* 5 (2021), 31. Publisher:Frontiers

MODELS	MACRO-F1	WEIGHTED-MACRO-F1	MICRO-F1
DANN-TOP-1	0,4465 ± 0,003	0,5873 ± 0,002	0,4563 ± 0,002
DANN-TOP-2	0,6007 ± 0,008	0,7307 ± 0,002	0,6154 ± 0,003
SciNoBo-CITREF-TOP-1	0,4627 ± 0,0	0,4900 ± 0,0	0,4900 ± 0,0
SciNoBo-CITREF-TOP-2	0,6000 ± 0,0	0,6208 ± 0,0	0,6177 ± 0,0
SciNoBo-REF-TOP-1	0,4781 ± 0,0	0,5000 ± 0,0	0,5022 ± 0,0
SciNoBo-REF-TOP-2	0,6190 ± 0,0	0,6277 ± 0,0	0,6205 ± 0,0
SciNoBo-PUB-TOP-1	0,7303 ± 0,0	0,7309 ± 0,0	0,7503 ± 0,0
SciNoBo-PUB-TOP-2	0,8200 ± 0,0	0,8223 ± 0,0	0,8270 ± 0,0

Figure 14: Macro-f1, Weighted-Macro-f1 and Micro-f1 scores. Best scores are shown in bold. DANN's experiments were repeated 4 times, and the averaged results are presented with standard deviation.

EVALUATION THROUGH THE PROJECT'S PILOTS

Beyond the experimental evaluation reported in the literature, the FoS classifier was also validated through its deployment within the SciLake project pilots. The classifier was applied to large collections of scientific publications relevant to the thematic domains addressed by the pilots. The results of these deployments are documented in this evaluation deliverable.

In practical terms, the FoS classifier served as a core component in the data preparation phase of the pilots. Specifically, the FoS classification results were used to:

- identify relevant scientific publications for each pilot domain,
- construct the initial corpus of publications used in the pilots (through OpenAIRE Explore),
- and support the creation of domain-specific knowledge graphs within the Scientific Lake infrastructure.

SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT GOALS CLASSIFIER

The Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) Classifier is an automated system designed to identify the thematic alignment of research outputs and projects with the 17 United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). The classifier supports large-scale analysis of research activities in relation to global societal challenges, enabling the monitoring of research contributions to sustainability priorities.

The SDG classifier operates primarily on textual descriptions of research outputs and projects, such as titles, abstracts, and objectives. By analysing these textual elements, the system assigns one or more SDG categories to each item, reflecting the inherently interdisciplinary

and cross-cutting nature of sustainability-related research. For the tool's methodology, please refer to D3.2.

EVALUATION

The SDG classifier was evaluated by applying it to a large corpus of European Union-funded research projects within the Horizon Europe programme. In this evaluation, the classifier analysed 5,426 projects, using concatenated project titles and objectives as input for the classification process.

The resulting classifications provided insights into the thematic distribution of projects across the SDG framework. The evaluation revealed that a significant proportion of projects could be meaningfully associated with one or more SDGs, with particularly strong representation observed in goals related to sustainability and environmental challenges. For example, many projects were associated with:

- SDG 7 – Affordable and Clean Energy
- SDG 11 – Sustainable Cities and Communities
- SDG 12 – Responsible Consumption and Production
- SDG 6 – Clean Water and Sanitation

This distribution reflects the thematic priorities of European research programmes, which emphasise sustainability, energy transition, and environmental resilience.

The evaluation also demonstrated the classifier's ability to capture the semantic characteristics of SDG-aligned projects. Visual analyses, such as word clouds generated from projects assigned to specific SDGs, confirmed that the dominant keywords correspond closely to the expected thematic areas. For instance, projects classified under SDG 4 (Quality Education) prominently featured terms such as "university," "science," and "education," while SDG 14 (Life Below Water) projects highlighted terms such as "marine," "ocean," and "ecological". These results provide qualitative evidence of the classifier's ability to correctly capture the thematic orientation of research projects.

In addition, the analysis highlighted the interconnected nature of SDG themes, with many projects assigned to multiple SDGs. Network visualisations of SDG co-occurrence showed strong relationships between goals, such as:

- SDG 7 (Affordable and Clean Energy) and SDG 13 (Climate Action),
- SDG 11 (Sustainable Cities and Communities) and SDG 12 (Responsible Consumption and Production),
- SDG 8 (Decent Work and Economic Growth) and SDG 9 (Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure).

These patterns illustrate the interconnected structure of sustainability challenges and confirm that the classifier effectively captures cross-domain relationships between SDG themes.

In addition to the evaluation described above, the SDG classifier was further validated through its deployment within the SciLake project pilots. Within these pilots, the classifier was applied to large collections of scientific publications to assess their alignment with the Sustainable Development Goals.

The results of these deployments were analysed as part of the project's overall evaluation activities and are documented in this evaluation deliverable. Importantly, the SDG classifier played a central role in the data preparation phase of the Energy pilot. The classifier was used to identify publications relevant to sustainability and energy-related SDGs, thereby enabling the creation of the pilot's initial corpus. This curated corpus served as the starting point for constructing the pilot's knowledge graph.

CITANCE ANALYSIS

The Citance Analysis Tool is designed to analyse the role and meaning of citations within scientific literature by automatically classifying citances (sentences containing references to other publications) across multiple analytical dimensions. Unlike traditional citation analysis approaches that focus solely on citation counts or sentiment, the tool introduces a multidimensional classification framework that captures the rhetorical and semantic characteristics of citation contexts.

- Specifically, the tool analyses citations along three complementary dimensions:
- Intent, which captures the rhetorical purpose of the citation,
- Semantics, which identifies the type of information referenced from the cited work,
- Polarity, which reflects the evaluative stance expressed toward the cited work.

This multidimensional representation enables a deeper understanding of how scientific knowledge is reused, compared, extended, or evaluated within scholarly communication.

EVALUATION DATASET

The evaluation of the Citance Analysis Tool was conducted using a manually annotated dataset consisting of 1,165 citances. Each citation was annotated according to the three classification dimensions: intent, semantics, and polarity.

Table 5: Annotated citations by Intent.

Intent Distribution

Intent Category	Instances	Percentage
Generic	603	51.76%
Reuse	237	20.35%
Comparison	225	19.31%
Extension	100	8.58%
Total	1165	100%

The results show that the majority of citations serve a generic referencing purpose, while a significant proportion are used to reuse prior work or compare different research approaches ([Table 5](#)).

Table 6: Annotated citations by Semantic.

Semantic Distribution

Semantic Category	Instances	Percentage
Methodology	361	30.99%
Artefact	346	29.70%
Claim	259	22.23%
Results	199	17.08%
Total	1165	100%

[Table 6](#) statistics indicate that citations most frequently refer to methods and research artefacts, such as tools, datasets, or software, which reflects the importance of methodological reuse in scientific research.

Table 7: Annotated citations by Intent.

Polarity Distribution

Polarity Category	Instances	Percentage
Neutral	826	70.90%
Supporting	183	15.71%
Refuting	156	13.39%
Total	1165	100%

The polarity distribution in [Table 7](#) highlights the predominance of neutral citations, which is consistent with the objective tone typically adopted in scientific writing.

[EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS](#)

The experimental evaluation involved testing different models (Transformer-based and LLMs); however, for simplicity, we present here the results of the model used in the SciLake project (a SciBERT-based multi-task classification model). SciBERT is a transformer-based language model pretrained on large-scale scientific corpora, which makes it particularly suitable for analysing scholarly texts.

The model was trained to jointly predict the three citance dimensions (intent, semantics, and polarity). Performance was evaluated using macro-F1, weighted F1, and classification accuracy.

Table 8: Semantic classifier results.

Semantic Classification Results

Metric	Score
Macro F1	77.39%
Weighted F1	78.25%
Accuracy	78.28%

The results in [Table 8](#) indicate that the classifier can reliably identify the type of scientific contribution referenced in a citation, such as methods, datasets, claims, or experimental findings.

Table 9: Intent classification results.

Intent Classification Results

Metric	Score
Macro F1	79.41%
Weighted F1	81.42%
Accuracy	81.97%

The high performance achieved in this task demonstrates the model's ability to accurately recognise the rhetorical purpose of citations in scientific texts ([Table 9](#)).

Table 10: Polarity Classification results

Polarity Classification Results

Metric	Score
Macro F1	56.83%
Weighted F1	69.44%
Accuracy	74.01%

Polarity classification in [Table 10](#) proved the most challenging task due to the subtle, often implicit evaluative language used in scientific discourse. Nevertheless, the classifier identified supporting and refuting citations with reasonable accuracy.

[EVALUATION THROUGH PILOTS](#)

The pilots conducted a structured evaluation of the Citance Analysis Tool by manually assessing a sample of automatically extracted citances according to a predefined annotation protocol. Each citance corresponds to a sentence containing a reference to another scientific work and was evaluated across three dimensions: Semantics, identifying the type of information referenced from the cited work (e.g., method, artifact, results, or claim); Intent, capturing the rhetorical purpose of the citation (e.g., reuse, comparison, extension, or generic background reference); and Polarity, indicating whether the citation expresses a supporting, refuting, or neutral stance toward the cited work. The evaluation dataset included identifiers

linking the citing and cited publications (SOURCE DOI and DEST DOI), along with the citation statement and its citation marker, enabling evaluators to assess the correctness of the automatically assigned labels based on the citation context.

Table 11: Citances analysis for the Energy pilot.

ENERGY EVALUATION

Pilot	Total Citances Evaluated	Semantics Correct	Intent Correct	Polarity Correct
Energy pilot	49	49 (100%)	49 (100%)	49 (100%)

Interpretation

The evaluation results in [Table 11](#) show perfect agreement between the tool's predictions and the expert annotations across all citations evaluated in the Energy pilot. All 49 citations were correctly classified by semantics, intent, and polarity, demonstrating that the Citance Analysis Tool performs extremely reliably on energy-related scientific literature in the evaluated dataset.

Table 12: Citances analysis for the Cancer pilot.

CANCER EVALUATION

Pilot	Total Citances Evaluated	Semantics Correct	Intent Correct	Polarity Correct
Cancer pilot	48	46 (95.8%)	45 (93.8%)	47 (97.9%)

Interpretation

The results in [Table 12](#) indicate a very strong performance of the Citance Analysis Tool in the Cancer pilot. Polarity classification achieved the highest agreement (97.9%), followed by semantic classification (95.8%) and intent classification (93.8%), demonstrating that the tool can reliably capture both the rhetorical function and evaluative stance of citations in biomedical literature.

Table 13: Citances analysis for the Neuroscience pilot.

NEUROSCIENCE

Pilot	Total Citances Evaluated	Semantics Correct	Intent Correct	Polarity Correct
Neuroscience pilot	48	42 (87.5%)	43 (89.6%)	46 (95.8%)

Interpretation

The Neuroscience pilot evaluation in [Table 13](#) included 48 citations, which were manually assessed by domain experts across the three analytical dimensions of the Citance Analysis tool: Semantics, Intent, and Polarity. The results show a high level of agreement between the automated predictions and expert annotations. Specifically, 42 citations were correctly classified in terms of semantics (87.5%), 43 citations in terms of intent (89.6%), and 46 citations in terms of polarity (95.8%). These findings indicate that the tool performs reliably in the neuroscience domain, particularly in identifying citation polarity, while maintaining strong performance in intent and semantic classification, demonstrating its suitability for supporting citation-context analysis in biomedical research literature.

Table 14: Citances analysis for the Transportation pilot.

TRANSPORTATION

Pilot	Total Citances Evaluated	Semantics Correct	Intent Correct	Polarity Correct
Maritime pilot	48	41 (85.4%)	44 (91.7%)	47 (97.9%)
CCAM pilot	48	40 (83.3%)	44 (91.7%)	47 (97.9%)

Interpretation

These results in [Table 14](#) show that the Citance Analysis Tool performs very strongly for intent and polarity classification, achieving over 90% agreement with expert annotations, while

semantic classification remains slightly more challenging but still achieves over 80% accuracy in both pilot domains.

RESEARCH ARTEFACT ANALYSIS

The Research Artefact Analysis (RAA) tool aims to automatically identify and extract references to research artefacts in scientific publications, with a primary focus on datasets and software resources. The tool extracts both the artefact mention and associated metadata, including the artefact name, version, license, URL, provenance, and usage. These elements are crucial for supporting reproducibility, transparency, and reuse of scientific outputs.

DATASET CONSTRUCTION AND AUGMENTATION

The original RAA approach introduced a dataset comprising synthetic and real snippets from scientific publications, annotated with mentions of research artefacts and associated metadata fields. The dataset was designed to capture both named and unnamed artefacts, addressing a limitation of many existing datasets that consider only explicitly named resources.

Each artifact mention includes the following metadata:

- Artefact type (dataset or software)
- Name
- Version
- License
- URL
- Provenance (whether the artefact was created by the authors)
- Usage (whether the artefact was used in the study)

The dataset construction involved a human-in-the-loop process in which synthetic examples were generated using large language models and then curated and expanded with real scientific text snippets.

Within the SciLake project, this dataset was further expanded through data augmentation, increasing the diversity of artefact mentions and improving coverage of different linguistic patterns found in scientific publications. The augmented dataset was subsequently used to train an updated artefact extraction model based on ModernBERT-Large in a Named Entity Recognition format, replacing earlier architectures used in previous experiments¹⁰.

¹⁰ [Empowering Knowledge Discovery from Scientific Literature: A novel approach to Research Artifact Analysis](#)

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The performance of the ModernBERT-Large model was evaluated on the augmented dataset. The following tables summarise the results for each extracted artefact attribute.

Table 15: Artefact Metadata Extraction Results.

Artefact Metadata Extraction Results

Metadata Field	Precision	Recall	F1 Score
URL	91.9%	92.3%	92.1%
Version	81.8%	80.1%	80.9%
License	95.8%	83.7%	89.3%
Name	85.7%	77.9%	81.6%

The results in [Table 15](#) indicate that the model performs particularly well in extracting URLs and licenses, which typically appear as clearly identifiable spans within scientific text. Extraction of artefact names is slightly more challenging due to variability in naming conventions and the presence of unnamed artefacts.

Artefact Usage and Provenance Classification

In addition to metadata extraction, the model was trained to identify whether the artefact was used by the authors or introduced by the publication.

Table 16: Artefact Usage and Provenance Classification.

Classification Task	Precision	Recall	F1 Score	Accuracy
Usage Detection	71.7%	84.8%	77.7%	70.8%
Provenance (Owned) Detection	92.8%	21.6%	35.1%	82.1%

The results in [Table 16](#) show that the model performs well at detecting artefact usage, although provenance classification remains more challenging, primarily because explicit statements indicating whether a resource was newly created by the authors are scarce.

Table 17: Overall NER Performance.

Overall NER Performance

Metric	Value
NER	98.2%
Macro F1 Score	87%

The high NER accuracy indicates that the model effectively identifies artefact-related entities within the scientific text, providing a reliable basis for downstream metadata extraction ([Table 17](#)).

[EVALUATION THROUGH PILOTS](#)

In addition to the experimental evaluation on the augmented dataset, the Research Artefact Analysis tool was evaluated in the SciLake project pilots, in which domain experts manually assessed the extracted artefacts.

The Cancer pilot performed a manual evaluation of the extracted artefacts using a dedicated annotation interface. During this process, evaluators reviewed artefact mentions identified by the tool and assessed their correctness.

However, an important limitation affected the evaluation results. A significant proportion of the extracted artefacts were unnamed, corresponding to implicit references such as “our dataset”, “the collected data”, or “the developed software”. Confirming the validity of these artefact mentions requires access to the full text of the publication, since the artefact name or description may appear elsewhere in the document. Annotators could not access the complete publication context while reviewing the extracted snippets. As a result, many unnamed artefacts could not be verified by the evaluators and were marked as false predictions.

5.4 End-to-end evaluation findings

The demonstrator phase evaluated the integrated use of SciLake services across all pilots, moving beyond component-level validation to assess the ecosystem's performance as a coherent knowledge management environment. While earlier evaluation activities focused on the correctness, robustness, and configuration of individual components, the demonstrators tested how these services interact within pilot-specific Scientific Knowledge Graphs to support realistic research workflows. This phase examined the system's ability to translate research questions into structured queries, combine semantic enrichment with graph exploration, and produce interpretable insights through user-facing interfaces. The following sections present the demonstrator results per pilot.

5.4.1 Energy

The demonstrator activities of the Energy pilot were conducted within a shorter timeframe than initially envisaged. The phased delivery and late-stage integration of several services reduced the duration available for extended iterative testing. Consequently, the demonstrator prioritised validating the functional integration of services and the feasibility of research workflows over large-scale benchmarking or extensive user testing.

The components required for a fully consolidated demonstrator environment—particularly the integrated graph infrastructure and enriched datasets—became operational only near the final reporting period. As a result, the demonstrator took the form of a capability-oriented validation, illustrating how available SciLake services can be combined to support realistic research workflows, rather than a long-term, stable demonstrator environment tested by a wide range of users. External expert validation could therefore not be included within the available timeframe.

Within this capability-oriented demonstrator, the [Energy Gateway](#) served as the primary foundation for the integrated workflow, as all downstream enrichment and graph functionalities depend on the selected corpus ([Figure 15](#)). Through successive refinements, disciplinary confounders associated with generic uses of the term “energy” (e.g., metabolism, physics, psychology) were significantly reduced, resulting in a dataset more closely aligned with regional energy planning research.

During this process, a representativity issue was identified in the temporal distribution of results. Further analysis showed that the apparent decrease in recent publications was primarily due to changes in subject-based tagging in the OpenAIRE selection criteria. In particular, the removal of the Field of Science category FoS 021108 – Energy left SDG 7 (Clean

Energy) as the dominant subject criterion. Since SDG annotations are ingested metadata with uneven coverage in recent years, this has affected the apparent volume of recent results. In addition, a temporary omission of Zenodo community tags during data import (later corrected) contributed to partial visibility gaps.

These findings indicate that the observed temporal decrease reflects constraints in metadata coverage rather than a decline in energy research activity. Despite these limitations, research-question-driven testing confirmed that the dataset remains sufficiently coherent to support meaningful knowledge graph construction and exploration.

Figure 15: Energy pilot gateway on OpenAIRE Connect.

Exploration through BIP! Spaces enabled examination of the dataset’s thematic, spatial, and temporal characteristics. The thematic coherence of the retrieved papers remained satisfactory and aligned with the intended scope of the Energy pilot.

In this context, the representativeness of the broader “energy” subject family functions as an entry point for researchers: it provides the first signal that the platform contains relevant material. While the OpenAIRE gateway provides structured access to the corpus, BIP! Spaces demonstrates the graph’s discovery capabilities through a user-friendly interface that supports intuitive exploration before users engage with more advanced graph-based operations.

Although the temporal completeness of the dataset depends on upstream metadata coverage and periodic refinement of the gateway, the overall corpus remains sufficiently robust to support domain-oriented exploration and knowledge graph development.

Initial integration testing in Neo4j verified the graph's internal structure, including entity relationships and query logic ([Figure 16](#)). While the use of Cypher queries and system dependencies (Linux/Docker environments) limited accessibility for non-technical users during early testing, this phase confirmed the structural integrity and interoperability of the graph components.

Later integration stages improved system maturity, although extensive user testing under fully stable conditions was constrained by the project timeline. Validation, therefore, focused on confirming cross-component interoperability rather than performing comprehensive usability benchmarking.

The integration of entity extraction services, including EnergyType, EnergyStorage, and Object of Study, demonstrated operational functionality within the graph environment ([Figure 16](#)). Geographic enrichment, considered particularly relevant to the Energy pilot, showed promising analytical potential for spatially grounded research questions, although its full potential would benefit from further testing.

Exploratory queries were used to retrieve relationships between entities and research outputs, such as the number of publications per geographic region, links between publications and specific energy technologies, and connections between geographic entities and energy technologies through research outputs ([Figure 17](#)). Example results were showcased at the final dissemination event of the SciLake project (March 2026) in the contribution [“Toward Mapping the Energy Research Landscape”](#). Limited experiments also compared query execution between Neo4j and AvantGraph instances.

Certain advanced features were not explored due to time constraints. These include the execution of native algorithms in AvantGraph, graph editing capabilities, and the modelling of spatial relationships between geographic entities. These aspects remain areas for future development.

Figure 16: Simplified Energy pilot SKG displaying nodes of enriched entities on Neo4j.

Figure 17: Geographic results of the Object of study entity in Europe for the “Solar photovoltaic entity”. The results display publication count aggregated per country.

Functional Readiness and Integration Value

Despite the shortened demonstrator phase, the Energy pilot confirmed that the integrated SciLake ecosystem is functionally capable of supporting multi-dimensional research workflows relevant to regional energy planning. The system enables researchers to translate research questions into structured queries, explore spatial and temporal patterns, categorise research outputs by energy technologies, and navigate relationships between enriched entities within a coherent graph structure.

While comprehensive coverage validation would require additional dataset expansion and further iterative refinement, the demonstrator successfully validated the functional readiness, architectural coherence, and cross-service interoperability of the SciLake ecosystem. The results demonstrate the platform's potential to support knowledge discovery and analytical exploration in energy research, while providing a clear direction for future consolidation and scaling.

5.4.2 Cancer

The Cancer pilot demonstrator results highlight the potential of the SciLake ecosystem to support knowledge discovery in the biomedical domain by integrating heterogeneous data sources into a coherent Science Cancer Knowledge Graph (SCKG). The developed SCKG, with a focus on Chronic Lymphocytic Leukaemia (CLL), combines information from the Clinical Knowledge Graph, OpenAIREGraph, and gene regulatory networks (GRNs) derived from cancer-specific multi-omics datasets. This integration enables the interconnection of genes, proteins, metabolites, drugs, and scientific publications, supporting systems-level exploration of cancer mechanisms.

During the evaluation, domain experts interacted with the SCKG through multiple access points, including graph queries, graph-based analysis, and literature exploration interfaces. The system demonstrated the ability to efficiently translate biological research questions into structured queries, allowing users to retrieve interconnected information across different biological entities. This significantly improved the accessibility of complex biomedical knowledge compared to isolated data sources.

The inclusion of GRNs derived from datasets such as BloodCancerMultiOmics2017 and reconstructed using established algorithms provided an additional layer of biological insight. These networks enabled users to explore relationships among molecular entities in the context of disease subtypes (e.g., aggressive versus indolent CLL), thereby supporting a more nuanced interpretation of disease mechanisms. At the same time, the integration of these datasets highlighted challenges related to data heterogeneity and the need for careful harmonisation across sources.

The use of SciLake services, including AvantGraph for graph exploration and algorithmic analysis, and BIP! Spaces for semantically enriched literature discovery further enhanced the system's usability. Graph-based analysis allowed the identification of clusters and interaction patterns within protein networks, supporting hypothesis generation. In parallel, literature exploration functionalities enabled users to identify relevant publications ranked by impact

and enriched with domain-specific annotations, facilitating contextual understanding of research findings.

Despite the limited testing period, the demonstrator confirmed that the integrated SciLake environment provides a valuable framework for cancer research. The combination of semantic enrichment, graph-based representation, and advanced querying capabilities enables users to explore complex biomedical relationships, efficiently identify relevant knowledge, and support the generation of new research hypotheses. The latter have been showcased in the [Cancer pilot dissemination presentation](#). These results indicate that the SCKG can serve as a flexible and extensible resource for precision oncology applications, with potential for further expansion through additional datasets and analytical methods.

5.4.3 Neuroscience

We aimed to show how the Neuroscience SKG within the SciLake ecosystem can answer practical questions to support discovery, impact assessment, and curation prioritisation. The Bip! Spaces provided an easy-to-use UI for keyword search, faceted filtering (including domain-specific entities), and ranking by impact indicators. Complementing the UI, Cypher queries against the SKG reliably returned publication–dataset linkages and citation counts attached to each product, enabling impact assessment ([Figure 18](#)). NER, using domain entities, supported the extraction of counts and top research products for specific topics (diseases, techniques, brain regions ([Figure 19](#)) and enabled comparative queries, such as gender balance across topic areas. We also used AvantGraph’s analytical capabilities to run PageRank and identify prominent research products in the graph. At the same time, several limitations constrained the scope and reliability of these analyses: topic labels were often too broad or not tightly aligned with neuroscience; author-level queries were unreliable because many records lacked ORCID identifiers; and dataset impact indicators were undermined by inconsistent citation practices across datasets.

Figure 18: An example research product and its relationships to other nodes in the SKG. *Linked nodes have been reduced for illustration.

Figure 19: Top 5 research products for 'medial entorhinal cortex' based on their citation counts

These demonstrators showed that linking heterogeneous research products via semantic entities and bibliographic relationships improves discoverability and information extraction. They also highlighted the SKG's potential to harmonise fragmented research outputs and make them more accessible, while underscoring the need for improved metadata quality,

broader use of persistent identifiers, and better citation practices. Demonstrators have also been showcased during the [Neuroscience pilot dissemination presentation](#).

5.4.3 Transportation

MARITIME

During the evaluation, domain experts interacted with the demonstrator by performing keyword searches and applying filters for publication year, access type, and domain-specific annotations. The system returned results enriched with metadata and semantic annotations extracted from the SKG, including vessel types and technology-related entities. These annotations enabled users to contextualise research outputs within the maritime domain and explore connections between publications, technologies, organisations, and research projects.

The demonstrator scenarios showed that integrating SKG-based annotations significantly improves the discoverability of maritime research topics. For example, searches related to maritime decarbonisation enabled users to quickly identify recent open-access publications and observe temporal trends in the research landscape. Similarly, queries combining concepts such as autonomous shipping and collision avoidance allowed users to explore publications associated with specific vessel types and analyse their citation impact. These results illustrate how semantic enrichment and KG relationships support the identification of relevant research outputs and facilitate the analysis of emerging technological trends.

In addition to discovering relevant publications, this demonstrator highlighted the usefulness of citation-based impact indicators integrated into the platform. These indicators enabled users to assess the relative influence of research outputs and identify influential papers within specific thematic areas of maritime transport research. The availability of different ranking schemes, such as popularity and influence, provided complementary perspectives for analysing research impact and relevance.

Overall, the demonstrator results confirm that integrating the SciLake services and the Maritime SKG provides a valuable environment for exploring maritime transport research. The demonstrator-related results have been showcased in the [Maritime Transportation pilot dissemination presentation](#). The system supports structured knowledge discovery by combining semantic annotations, citation-based analytics, and graph-based relationships between research artefacts. As a result, stakeholders can more easily identify relevant literature, analyse technological developments, and gain insights into the evolving landscape of maritime transport research.

CCAM

CCAM evaluation results are high-quality and contextually relevant to the sector, with very few false positives and duplicates. In the former case, other Fields of Study or Technologies may appear that are partially related to the queried term(s), such as Lidar sensors in fields beyond CCAM. In the latter case, the use of two distinct sources (project SINFONICA and the FAME CCAM Knowledge Base) created the ecosystem's taxonomy, occasionally returning duplicate registries. This was a deliberate decision made during the evaluation process to check which source is identified each time. Also, the fact that the whole ecosystem referenced CCAM-related sources exclusively enhanced the results' relevance, prioritising quality over quantity.

All possible means of conducting research (keyword searches via GUI, queries in graph language, internal post-processing entity extraction, etc.) provide an integrated environment for accomplishing any potential research activity, directly or indirectly. Searching and querying give direct results, while the annotations and the several filtering options (citation, impulse, popularity, etc.) reveal knowledge not intended beforehand, adding value to the ecosystem.

The applied co-creation procedure between the CCAM community, which acknowledges real research needs, and the technical tool developers, through several rounds of consultation, was the key to creating an effective research ecosystem. As a result, it may be expanded to external CCAM environments and to host research for any interested stakeholder (a one-stop shop for CCAM research). Also, the demonstrator-related activities have been showcased in the [CCAM Transportation pilot dissemination presentation](#).

6. Conclusions

Deliverable D5.2 documents the evaluation of the SciLake ecosystem across four domain-specific pilots: Neuroscience, Cancer, Energy, and Transportation. Building upon the preparatory activities described in Deliverable D5.1, this report presents the implementation of roadmap actions, component-level validation activities, and integrated demonstrator testing conducted under realistic research conditions.

Across pilots, the evaluation confirmed that the modular architecture of the SciLake ecosystem enables the configuration of domain-specific Scientific Knowledge Graphs (SKGs) and supports the enrichment of research artefacts through semantic annotation, entity extraction, citation analysis, and structured exploration services. The pilots demonstrated that meaningful research workflows can be supported by combining gateway configuration, enriched entities, semantic linking, and user-facing interfaces. In particular, the integration of domain taxonomies, structured entity recognition, and graph-based exploration mechanisms provides a foundation for advanced knowledge discovery beyond traditional bibliographic search.

The component-level evaluations presented in this deliverable provide evidence of the technical maturity and practical relevance of several key services within the ecosystem. Experimental evaluations confirmed the effectiveness of domain-adapted machine translation models for scientific texts, while classification and annotation components demonstrated strong performance in identifying research artefacts, scientific fields, and Sustainable Development Goal alignments. In addition, user-based evaluation activities conducted through interfaces such as BIP! Spaces showed high acceptance of ranking schemes and semantic annotations across most pilots, confirming the usefulness of impact-based ranking indicators and domain-specific entity enrichment for knowledge discovery tasks.

At the same time, the evaluation process highlighted several areas where configuration choices, metadata coverage, and domain-specific interpretation influence system performance and usability. Pilot activities revealed that the quality and interpretability of semantic annotations depend not only on extraction accuracy but also on contextual relevance and clear modelling decisions within the knowledge graph. Similarly, the construction of domain-oriented datasets, such as those produced through gateway configurations, requires iterative refinement to balance thematic coverage and precision. These findings underline the importance of close collaboration between technical developers and domain experts, ensuring that automated extraction and classification outputs remain aligned with real research practices.

The demonstrator activities provided further validation of the ecosystem from an integrated perspective. Although the effective testing period was shorter than initially planned due to the phased delivery of some services, the pilots demonstrated that SciLake components can operate together to support multi-dimensional exploration of scientific knowledge, including thematic, spatial, temporal, and institutional perspectives. The demonstrators illustrated how researchers can move from structured queries to semantically enriched insights by combining gateway configuration, entity extraction, knowledge graph navigation, and impact-based ranking mechanisms.

Overall, the evaluation results confirm the conceptual validity and operational feasibility of the SciLake ecosystem as a modular infrastructure for knowledge discovery and for constructing scientific knowledge graphs. While further iterative refinement, dataset expansion, and long-term user testing would strengthen quantitative validation, the pilots have demonstrated that the integrated platform can support domain-oriented research exploration and advanced analytical workflows. The results, therefore, provide a solid basis for future development, scaling, and adoption of SciLake services within broader research communities.

DRAFT